

Miscellaneous notes on probabilities, calculus and computing*

Xuejun Dong
Texas A&M AgriLife Research
Uvalde, TX 78801
e-mail: xuejun.dong@ag.tamu.edu

Contents

1	Basics of combinatorics	3
2	Probabilities assigned to events	4
3	Simulating nonuniform distributions	8
4	Monte Carlo method for approximating a nonrandom quantity	10
5	Other comments on stochastic tools	14
6	State estimation through filtering	19
6.1	Bayesian state estimator	19
6.2	The derivations of the prior and posterior pdf's	20
6.3	Particle filtering for numerical Bayesian estimation	23
7	Limit and continuation	24
8	Numerical evaluation of definite integrals	26
9	Review of differential equations	29
9.1	Simple differential equations: Howard Anton 3rd ed.	29
9.2	Linear differentiation equations of order greater than one	33
10	Differences between function and subroutine in structured programs	41

*Created: April 1, 2009 / Last modified: July 2, 2025

11	How to run a Fortran program on a Windows computer	44
11.1	Basics	44
11.2	Compiling subroutines together with the main program, or separately	45
11.2.1	Compiling with the main program	46
11.2.2	Compiling separately and then linked to the main program	46
11.3	Using gfortran under Cygwin	47
11.4	Using g77 under Cygwin	47
12	Matlab for scientific computing	49
12.1	Basics	49
12.2	Scripts and functions	50
12.3	Matlab data types	54
12.4	Matlab programming tips	57
12.5	Matlab graphing tips	58
12.6	Cell publishing	59
12.6.1	Integrate a function	60
12.6.2	Plot the results	60
13	Optimization through computing	62
13.1	Relative role of stomata on transpiration and assimilation	62
13.2	Dynamic optimization	65
13.3	Linear programming	66
13.4	Dealing with unrestricted variables	72
13.5	Duality in Linear programming	77
13.6	Further notes on optimization-related concepts	80
14	Calculus of variations and dynamic control theory	81
15	Appendix	84
15.1	An Example for simulating a normal distribution using MINITAB	84
15.2	An Example of rejection sampling for simulating an arbitrary distribution	84
15.3	Evaluating a definite integral by sampling a uniform distribution	85
15.4	Evaluating a definite integral by sampling an exponential distribution	86
15.5	Evaluating a definite integral by sampling a normal distribution	87
15.6	Evaluating a definite integral using the transformation method and the trapezoidal rule	89
15.7	A True Basic program for approximating the value of pi	90
15.8	A MINITAB macro for approximating the volume of a ball with radius 1	91
15.9	A MINITAB macro for approximating the value of e using the Monte Carlo method	92
15.10A	MINITAB macro for recursively simulating a posterior probability	93
15.11A	MINITAB macro for simulating transpiration ratio of plant leaves	94
15.12A	MINITAB macro for carrying out pivoting in solving a system of linear equations	98

In stochastic modeling, it is useful to be able to simulate a statistical distribution on the computer. This note summarizes some useful results based my study of the relevant materials from Evans and Rosenthal (2006)¹, Giordano and Nakanishi (2006)², Chorin and Hald (2006)³, and Simon (2006)⁴. I will also discuss a few interesting ideas related to some other stochastic tools, such as data assimilation and optimal state estimation, according to presentations in Chorin and Hald (2006) and Simon (2006).

1 Basics of combinatorics

Now we summarize the key ideas on pages 14–17 of ER (2006) about basic principles of *combinatorics*⁵:

- *Counting sequences and multiplication principle.* If we flip three fair coins and roll two six-sided fair dice, the total number of outcomes is $2 \times 2 \times 2 \times 6 \times 6 = 288$.
- *Counting permutations.* Permutations are sequences of elements from a set where no element appears more than once. Suppose we have n jackets and will randomly give each of them to n people. Let's count how many ways we can do this. There are n ways for the first person to get a jacket, $n - 1$ ways for the second person to get a jacket,..., and only one way for the last person. So, there are total $n!$ (n factorial) ways of different combinations (permutations). If we have n jackets and want to give them to k people ($k \leq n$), then we have total of $n(n - 1) \dots (n - (k - 1))$ ways, or $\frac{n!}{(n-k)!}$ ways, to distribute the n jackets to k people.
- *Counting subsets*⁶. This discussion will lead to the *binomial coefficient*

$$\binom{n}{k} = \frac{n!}{k!(n-k)!}, \quad (1)$$

as well as the *binomial distribution function*

$$f_X(k) = \binom{n}{k} \theta^k (1 - \theta)^{n-k} = \frac{n!}{k!(n-k)!} \theta^k (1 - \theta)^{n-k}, \quad (2)$$

where the discrete random variable X is said to have a binomial distribution, that is, $X \sim \text{Binomial}(n, \theta)$. Consider the problem of flipping 10 fair coins and calculating the

¹M. J. Evans and J. S. Rosenthal, 2006. Probability and Statistics: The Science of Uncertainty. W. H. Freeman and Company, New York, NY. pp685.

²N. J. Giordano and H. Nakanishi, 2006. Computational Physics. Pearson Education, Inc. Upper Saddle River, NJ. 2nd edition, pp544.

³A. J. Chorin and O. H. Hald, 2006. Stochastic Tools in Mathematics and Science. Springer Science + Business Media, Inc. New York, NY. pp147.

⁴D. Simon, 2006. Optimal State Estimation. John Wiley & Sons, Inc. Hoboken, New Jersey.

⁵"The science of counting is called combinatorics." -ER

⁶We treat this problem slightly differently from that of ER (2006), so that the mechanism of computation becomes clearer.

probability that exactly seven of them are heads. First let's think about this problem in line of giving 7 people each a jacket from 10 different jackets, as discussed above. The rationale is that there are 10 heads in total here and we want to know the probability of having exactly 7 heads in 10 trials. From our discussion of counting permutations, we know that there are $\frac{10!}{(10-7)!}$ different ways of giving 7 people each a jacket from 10 jackets. However, we must see that there is a big difference between jacket distribution and coin flipping problem here: in the former, each person is different; but in the latter (coin problem), having 7 heads show up is enough and we don't care about the detailed permutations within the selected 7 heads⁷. We are only interested in the *ways* to get the desired result. Because exactly 7! different permutations (for a particular combination of having 7 heads show up) are considered as one same way. So eventually, we have $\frac{10!}{(10-7)!7!} = 120$ ways that 7 of the 10 coin flips are heads after repeatedly doing this experiment many times. This is Equation 1, which says that if we flip 10 fair coins many times, there are $\frac{10!}{(10-7)!7!} = 120$ ways of obtaining exact seven heads.

Because all the 10 coins are fair⁸ and the event that either a head or a tail occurs for a particular flipping trial is independent. So, the probability of obtaining *one set* of 7 heads and 3 tails is $(\frac{1}{2})^7(\frac{1}{2})^{10-7}$. Considering our discussion in the last paragraph, there are $\frac{10!}{(10-7)!7!} = 120$ sets of this kind of combinations that meet our definition of "exactly seven of them are heads", so the final answer to this coin flipping problem is $\frac{10!}{(10-7)!7!}(\frac{1}{2})^7(\frac{1}{2})^{10-7}$.

Now, suppose all the 10 coins are the same but are not fair, with a probability of showing the head of θ . Because there are only 2 possible outcomes, the probability of showing the tail is thus $1 - \theta$. Then our final probability for obtaining exactly seven heads after flipping the 10 coins is $\frac{10!}{(10-7)!7!}\theta^7(1 - \theta)^{10-7}$. Finally, assume we have n such kind of coins to flip and the probability of obtaining exactly k heads ($k \leq n$) is then determined by Equation 2.

2 Probabilities assigned to events

Here are some notes based on studying the textbook written by Paul G. Hoel, Sidney C. Port and Charles J. Stone (1971)⁹. The book provides a clear discussion of basic theories of probabilities from applied frequentist perspective. To study the rules governing the occurrence of chance variables, we first need to define the outcomes of (imagined) *random experiment* leading to the occurrence of the chance variables. Here the use of *random experiment* signifies the situation in which a random variable is used to represent the possible outcomes of a repeating trial and the likelihood of different outcomes of the variable is described using

⁷Imagine that each of the 10 heads are labeled uniquely and we can always find out which 7 heads show up in a particular trial of flipping 10 fair coins and obtaining a result as described in this problem.

⁸That means for each of them it is equally likely to obtain a head or tail; the probability of obtaining a head or tail is 1/2.

⁹Introduction to Probability Theory, Houghton Mifflin Company, Boston, USA. 1971

probability laws. The different outcomes of a random experiment are collectively referred to as events that are modeled as sets. The probability space Ω is defined as the union of all possible outcomes (subsets) of the random experiment. In particular, if Ω is partitioned into two disjoint sets A and B , then the following relation is held:

$$P(\Omega) = P(A) + P(B), \quad (3)$$

where $P(\Omega) = 1$, as any point of event will have to be included in Ω .

Some important lessons learned in this chapter include (a) probabilities of disjoint sets, (b) conditional probabilities, and (c) probabilities of independent events. Here “sets” and “events” are used interchangeably.

1. Probabilities of disjoint sets. If two sets (events), A and B , are disjoint, then $P(A \cup B) = P(A) + P(B)$. Otherwise, more generally, $P(A \cup B) = P(A) + P(B) - P(A \cap B)$. This also means that to say the two sets are disjoint is equivalent as saying that they do not have common elements (or, the set of their intersection is empty set, i.e., $P(A \cap B) = \emptyset$).
2. Conditional probabilities¹⁰. This is defined as the probability of having one event occurring given that the other event has occurred. The conditional probability of A given B is defined as

$$P(A|B) = \frac{P(A \cap B)}{P(B)}. \quad (4)$$

An important extension of conditional probability is the Bayes’s rule, which is discussed in the book of Hoel et al. (1971) as follows: Suppose A_1, A_2, \dots, A_n are n mutually disjoint events with union Ω . Let B be an event such that $P(B) > 0$ and suppose $P(B|A_k)$ and $P(A_k)$ are specified for $1 \leq k \leq n$. The Probability of $P(A_i|B)$ is calculated as

$$P(A_i|B) = \frac{P(A_i \cap B)}{P(B)} = \frac{P(A_i)P(B|A_i)}{\sum_{k=1}^n P(A_k)P(B|A_k)} \quad (5)$$

Hoel et al. (1971) gives a way to interpret Equation 5:

Suppose we think of the events A_k as being the possible “causes” of the observable event B . Then $P(A_i|B)$ is the probability that the event A_i was the “cause” of B given that B occurs.

3. Probabilities of independent events. The two events A and B are independent if and only if

$$P(A \cap B) = P(A)P(B). \quad (6)$$

To say two events A and B are independent is equivalent as saying that the conditional probability $P(A|B)$ is the same as the unconditional probability $P(A)$.

¹⁰There is a very good, intuitive discussion of conditional probability on page 14 of Hoel et al. (1971). Introduction to Probability Theory. Houghton Mifflin Company. Boston, USA.

The following are solutions to selected problems of **Chapter 1** of Hoel et al. (1971):

- **Problem 27.** A college is composed of 70% men and 30% women. It is known that 40% of men and 60% of women smoke cigarettes. What is the probability that a student observed smoking a cigarette is a man?

Let's denote M as the event that a student is male and F the event that the student is female at this college. Also let's define S as the event that a student selected smokes and N as the event that a student selected does not smoke. Apparently gender and smoking habit describe two different aspects of the student population at this college. We require that $\Omega = M \cup F = S \cup N$. Now let's assign probabilities to events: $P(M) = 0.7$, $P(F) = 0.3$, $P(S|M) = 0.4$, and $P(S|F) = 0.6$. Our problem is to find $P(M|S)$. According to the definition of conditional probability,

$$P(M|S) = \frac{P(M \cap S)}{P(S)}. \quad (7)$$

Applying rule of conditional probability to $P(S|M)$ allows us to find the numerator of Equation 7, i.e., $P(M \cap S) = P(M)P(S|M) = 0.7 \times 0.4 = 0.28$. Also, $P(F \cap S)$ can be computed similarly as $P(F \cap S) = P(F)P(S|F) = 0.3 \times 0.6 = 0.18$. The denominator of Equation 7 can be resolved by considering set S (event that a student smokes) as union of two disjoint sets $S \cap M$ and $S \cap F$:

$$\begin{aligned} P(S) &= P(S \cap M) + P(S \cap F) \\ &= 0.28 + 0.18 \\ &= 0.46. \end{aligned}$$

As a result, $P(M|S) = P(M \cap S)/P(S) = 14/23$.

- **Problem 37.** Experience shows that 20% of people reserving tables at certain restaurant never show up. If the restaurant has 50 tables and takes 52 reservations, what is the probability that it will be able to accommodate everyone?

The probability that the restaurant will be able to accommodate everyone is the one that at least two people who placed reservations do not show up. Let's denote the event that at least two people who placed reservations do not show up as C . Now let's consider A as the event that nobody who made the reservation failed to show up (or all 52 people show up). This is the first situation that the restaurant cannot accommodate everyone. The second situation that it cannot accommodate everyone is the one in which exactly one person who made the reservation did not show up. Let's use B to denote the event of this second situation. We know that $\Omega = A \cup B \cup C$. So the required probability can be calculated as $P(C) = 1 - P(A) - P(B)$, because A , B , and C are disjoint sets.

$$P(A) = \binom{52}{0} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{5}\right)^0 \left(\frac{4}{5}\right)^{52} = \left(\frac{4}{5}\right)^{52}$$

and

$$P(B) = \binom{52}{1} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{5}\right) \left(\frac{4}{5}\right)^{51} = \frac{52}{5} \left(\frac{4}{5}\right)^{51}$$

As a result, the required probability can be found as

$$\begin{aligned} P(C) &= 1 - P(A) - P(B) \\ &= 1 - \left(\frac{4}{5}\right)^{52} - \frac{52}{5} \left(\frac{4}{5}\right)^{51} \\ &= 1 - \left(\frac{4}{5}\right)^{52} \cdot \frac{56}{5}. \end{aligned}$$

- **Problem 44.** A man fires 12 shots independently at a target. What is the probability that he hits the target at least once if he has probability $9/10$ of hitting the target on any given shot?

Let W denote the event that the man hits the target at least once, and let N denote the event the he hits nothing. We can envision that W and N are disjoint sets. So we have $\Omega = N \cup W$, and $P(\Omega) = P(N) + P(W)$. So, the required probability is calculated as

$$\begin{aligned} P(W) &= 1 - P(N) \\ &= 1 - \binom{12}{0} \cdot \left(\frac{9}{10}\right)^0 \left(\frac{1}{10}\right)^{12} \\ &= 1 - \left(\frac{1}{10}\right)^{12}. \end{aligned}$$

- **Problem 46.** Suppose the probability of hitting a target is $1/4$. If eight shots are fired at the target, what is the probability that the target is hit at least twice?

Let's consider A as the event that the person hits zero target in 8 shots; B as the event that he hits one target in 8 shots. So, the probability that he hits at least two targets in 8 shots is calculated as $P(T) = 1 - P(A) - P(B)$, as A and B are disjoint sets.

$$P(A) = \binom{8}{0} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{4}\right)^0 \left(\frac{3}{4}\right)^8 = \left(\frac{3}{4}\right)^8$$

and

$$P(B) = \binom{8}{1} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{4}\right) \left(\frac{3}{4}\right)^7 = 2 \left(\frac{3}{4}\right)^7$$

As a result, the required probability can be found as

$$\begin{aligned}
 P(T) &= 1 - P(A) - P(B) \\
 &= 1 - \left(\frac{3}{4}\right)^8 - 2\left(\frac{3}{4}\right)^7 \\
 &= 1 - \left(\frac{3}{4}\right)^7 \cdot \frac{11}{4}.
 \end{aligned}$$

3 Simulating nonuniform distributions

If we can simulate a random variable with uniform distribution, denoted as Uniform $[0,1]$, then we can obtain continuous random variables with different distributions. There three common methods for doing this: (a) the *transformation method*; (b) *rejection method*; and (c) *Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) resampling method*. These are discussed in Giordano and Nakanishi (2006) and in Evans and Rosenthal (2006). We first consider the transformation method and the rejection method but will pick up the MCMC method in a later section. The transformation method relies on the use of the inversion of functions. However, it involves the evaluation of functions, which can be difficult sometimes. The rejection method, on the other hand, can be used for any distribution, even those with arbitrary densities.

Evans and Rosenthal (2006) give three important theorems for simulating nonuniform distributions based on the change of variables (Theorems 2.6.2, 2.6.3 and 2.6.4 on pages 73-75). These can be summarized as a single rule. Let X be a continuous random variable with density f_X . Let $Y = h(X)$ be a monotonous (decreasing or increasing) function for $x \geq 0$. Then Y is also a continuous random variable with density defined by

$$f_Y(y) = f_X(h^{-1}(y))/|h'(h^{-1}(y))|, \quad (8)$$

where h' is the derivative of $y = h(x)$, and $h^{-1}(y)$ is the unique x that satisfies $h(x) = y$.

Evans and Rosenthal (2006) also give the following examples. Suppose U_1 is a random variable uniformly distributed on $[0,1]$, then we can do the following to obtain several other continuous distributions:

- The uniform $[L,R]$ distribution: Calculate $X = (R-L)U_1 + L$, then $X \sim \text{Uniform}[L,R]$, meaning X is uniformly distributed on interval $[L,R]$ with a density function of

$$f(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{R-L} & \text{if } L \leq x \leq R \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

Apparently, the density for Uniform $[0,1]$ is

$$f(x) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } 0 \leq x \leq 1 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

- The exponential(λ) distribution: Calculate $X = \ln(1/U_1)/\lambda$, then $X \sim \text{Exponential}(\lambda)$. In particular, if $\lambda = 1$, we will have $X \sim \text{Exponential}(1)$. The density for exponential(λ) distribution is

$$f(x) = \begin{cases} \lambda e^{-\lambda x} & \text{if } x \geq 0 \\ 0 & \text{if } x < 0. \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

And the density for exponential(1) is

$$f(x) = \begin{cases} e^{-x} & \text{if } x \geq 0 \\ 0 & \text{if } x < 0. \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

- The $N(\mu, \sigma^2)$ distribution: Suppose we have two independent uniform distributions, $U_1 \sim \text{Uniform}[0,1]$ and $U_2 \sim \text{Uniform}[0,1]$. Then we can easily obtain two independent normal distributions

$$X = \sqrt{-2\log(U_1)} \cos(2\pi U_2), \quad Y = \sqrt{-2\log(U_1)} \sin(2\pi U_2) \quad (13)$$

where $\log()$ is for natural logarithm. That is, we have $X \sim N(0,1)$ and $Y \sim N(0,1)$. Further, if we want to get another normally distributed random variable Z with mean μ and standard deviation σ , we simply use $Z = \sigma X + \mu$, then $Z \sim N(\mu, \sigma^2)$. The density for $Z \sim N(\mu, \sigma^2)$ is defined as

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma} e^{-(x-\mu)^2/(2\sigma^2)}. \quad (14)$$

A computer example for simulating a normal distribution is shown in Appendix 15.1.

Appendix 15.2 contains an example using the rejection method to get a sample of an arbitrarily specified distribution. Here for simplicity we choose to use the example provided in Giordano and Nakanishi (2006), page 518, to show how to generate a normal distribution with a mean and standard deviation of 1. We know that for random variable x , the probability $P(X = x)$ equals zero at any point x so that the integral of the density from $-\infty$ to ∞ will yield 1. However, the density of $f(x)$ has a defined value at particular point of the defined range of x . This method first generates a value of density for a chosen x , then compares this particular density value with a uniformly distributed random number drawn from the range of zero and a maximum value of the density from the theoretical distribution that we are going to generate numerically. In particular it proceeds in the following four steps:

1. Specify the density and range of interest of the distribution. Suppose we decide to sample a distribution with a density function of $f_X(x)$ for a random variable X between x_{min} and x_{max} .
2. Use a computer (such as RND function in True Basic or Rand() in C) to generate a sequence of random numbers $\{x_1, x_2, \dots\}$ uniformly distributed in the range of x_{min} and x_{max} .

3. Find the maximum value of $f_X(x)$ in the range of x_{min} and x_{max} . Denote this maximum value as f_{max} .
4. Pick a number x_i and evaluate $f_X(x_i)$. Now generate a new random variable X_{test} using the uniform distribution in the range of $[0, f_{max}]$. If $f_X(x_i) < X_{test}$, remove x_i from the list of the uniformly distributed random number list $\{x_1, x_2, \dots\}$; otherwise keep x_i in the list. After the process is repeated for all members of $\{x_1, x_2, \dots\}$, the numbers that remain in the list will have a distribution according $f_X(x)$, instead of the uniform distribution, according to which the list was originally generated. This makes sense from a probabilistic point of view. For example, if $f_X(x_i)$ is very close to f_{max} , it is more likely that x_i is to be kept in the list. On the other hand, if $f_X(x_i)$ is so low that it is close to zero, then it is more likely that x_i is to be removed from the list following the test. In other words, the acceptance probability $Prob[f_X(x_i) \geq X_{test}]$ approaches $\frac{f_X(x_i)}{f_{max}}$.

4 Monte Carlo method for approximating a nonrandom quantity

The Monte Carlo method for approximating definite integrals can be understood by the way how statistical expectations are defined for random variables and their functions. If η is a random variable with probability density function (pdf) of $f(x)$, that is,

$$f_\eta(x) = \begin{cases} f(x) & \text{if } a \leq x \leq b \\ 0 & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

then the expected value of η is defined as

$$E[\eta] = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} x f(x) dx. \quad (16)$$

Also, if $g(x)$ is a continuous function defined on the range of η , then $g(x)$ is also a random variable, and

$$E[g(\eta)] = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} g(x) f(x) dx. \quad (17)$$

Now let's see how the Monte carlo methods works when it is used to approximate a definite integral. Suppose we have an integral (may be a quite complex one for which a analytic solution is difficult to obtain) $I = \int_a^b g(x) f(x) dx$, where $f(x) \geq 0$ and $\int_a^b f(x) dx = 1$. According to the definition of expectation (Equation (17)), as well as the pdf of η (Equation 15), we have

$$I = \int_a^b g(x) f(x) dx = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} g(x) f(x) dx = E[g(\eta)], \quad (18)$$

where η is a random variable with density $f(x)$. Now suppose we can conduct n independent experiments so that we can obtain n measurements of η , which are $\eta_1, \eta_2, \dots, \eta_n$. Then the integral I can be estimated by

$$I = E[g(\eta)] = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n g(\eta_i). \quad (19)$$

Because η is distributed according to the density defined by $f(x)$, we can always sample η based on a sample of uniformly distributed random variable ξ (on interval $[0,1]$), provided that we can find a function $\eta = h(\xi)$. This can be done if we set the cumulative distribution function of η as $F(\eta) = \int_{-\infty}^{\eta} f(x) dx = \xi$, and solve for η as $\eta = F^{-1}(\xi)$. The error in this approximation (Equation 19) is in the order of $\sigma(g(\eta))/\sqrt{n}$.

The above error estimation is obtained by considering the variance of sums of random variables $g(\eta_i)$. Here $g(\eta_i)$'s are random variables because η_i 's are random variables (a function of a random variable is also a random variable). Because η_i 's are independent, $g(\eta_i)$'s are also independent. Further more, they are *identically* distributed random variables. So they are *iid* (independent, identically distributed) random variables. This means $Var(g(\eta_i)) = Var(g(\eta_1))$. As a result, we have

$$Var\left\{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n g(\eta_i)\right\} = \frac{1}{n^2} n Var(g(\eta_1)) = \frac{1}{n} Var(g(\eta_1)), \quad (20)$$

where $Var()$ stands for variance of a random variable. Taking square root for both sides of Equation (20), we have

$$\sqrt{Var\left\{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n g(\eta_i)\right\}} = \frac{\sqrt{Var(g(\eta_1))}}{\sqrt{n}} = \frac{\sigma(g(\eta_1))}{\sqrt{n}}. \quad (21)$$

According to the central limit theorem (page 209, Evans and Rosenthal, 2004), with a large n , the standard deviation of the estimation, σ in Equation 21, can be computed as

$$\sigma = \sqrt{M_n(1 - M_n)}, \quad (22)$$

where M_n is the average of $g(\eta_i)$, $i = 1, \dots, n$. It is clear that an increased sampling number n and a decreased error in the sampled $g(\eta_i)$ both contribute to the reduction in errors in the estimation of the integral using the Monte Carlo method. Methods such as *importance sampling* or *Markov chain Monte Carlo* might be used to get samples with reduced errors. Also there are other methods, as shown in the book *Numerical Recipes*, that can be used for a more efficient calculation using the Monte Carlo method by further reducing the estimation errors with moderate computing time. As emphasized by Giordano and Nakanishi (2006), Monte Carlo method gets more and more efficient for sampling in higher dimensional systems, because the estimation error is not a function of dimension but in the order of $1/\sqrt{n}$. For example, in theoretical physics, when dimension is higher than 4, the Monte Carlo method become more efficient than some other methods of numerical integration, such as Simpson's rule, etc.

Now we evaluate several definite integrals using the Monte Carlo method. These three examples are due to Evans and Rosenthal (2006), but we will do it with MINITAB. The general method is outlined in Section 5.

- Using uniform distribution to evaluate integral $I = \int_0^1 \cos(x^2) \sin(x^4) dx$. This is shown in Appendix 15.3. We can see that with the increase of n , the approximation gets more accurate, as can be seen from the error estimate, $M_n \pm 3S/\sqrt{n}$, where M_n and S are mean and standard deviation, respectively. Because uniform density has a value of $f(x) = 1$ (see Equation 10), any integral $I = \int_0^1 g(x) dx$ can be evaluated using the Monte Carlo method by sampling many replicates of η_i from uniform distribution and approximating the integral as $I = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n g(\eta_i)$. However, as discussed in Chorin and Hald (2006), some components of $g(x)$ (such as e^x) might induce a large standard error in the Monte Carlo sampling (Equation 21) and thus compromise the efficiency of this method. Importance sampling may be used to address this issue. Also, the sampling errors may be reduced by sampling from distributions other than the uniform distribution, provided $g(x)$ has appropriate terms representing the densities of those other distributions. We will see three examples below.
- Using exponential distribution to evaluate integral $I = \int_0^\infty 25x^2 \cos(x^2) e^{-25x} dx$. Because the density of exponential(25) is $25e^{-25x}$ for $x \geq 0$, the integral I can be written as

$$I = \int_0^\infty x^2 \cos(x^2) (25e^{-25x}) dx = E[X^2 \cos(x^2)], \quad (23)$$

where $X \sim \text{Exponential}(25)$. The MINITAB for this example code is shown in Appendix 15.4. The method for obtaining an exponential distribution based on a sample of uniform distribution is discussed in Section 3.

- Using normal distribution to evaluate integral $I = \int_0^\infty \sin(x) e^{-x^2/2} dx$. This can be done by sampling two independent uniform distributions using Equation 13. The MINITAB code for implementing this example is shown in Appendix 15.5.
- Using normal distribution to evaluate integral $I = \int_0^1 \sin(x) e^{-x^2/2} dx$. This is illustrated in Appendix 15.6. Note that the macro also evaluates the integral using the trapezoidal rule as a comparison. With $n = 10000$, the transformation method evaluates integral as $I \approx 0.36655$, with a standard error (σ) of 0.0144567 (thus a lower and higher bounds as 0.352198 and 0.381112, respectively). The result from the trapezoidal rule is $I \approx 0.364344$.

The next two examples (Appendices 15.7 and 15.8) show how to calculate the area and volume of geometric shapes using Monte Carlo method. By calculating the area of a circle with radius 1, we approximate the value of π (see Table 1). The True Basic code is listed in Appendix 15.7. The program runs faster in True Basic (15 seconds) than in MINITAB.

The volume of a ball is approximated using the Monte Carlo method. The code is shown in Appendix 15.8. A simulation result is shown in Table 2.

Table 1: Approximating the value of π using the Monte Carlo method.

N	<i>Estimated π</i>
100	3
500	3.184
1000	3.152
1500	3.2053333
3000	3.1586667
5000	3.1624
7500	3.1669333
10000	3.1392
10500	3.1295238
12000	3.1183333
15000	3.1237333
20000	3.1614
50000	3.13504
100000	3.14912
150000	3.1394133

Table 2: Approximating the volume of a ball with radius 1 using the Monte Carlo method.

N	<i>Estimated volume</i>	<i>True volume</i>
5000	4.16160	4.18879
20000	4.20000	4.18879

Table 3: Approximating the value of e using the Monte Carlo method.

N	<i>Estimated</i>	<i>True value</i>
1000	2.48380	2.71828
10000	2.61218	2.71828
20000	2.61856	2.71828

Finally, the value of e is approximated by evaluating the integral $I = \int_1^{10} \frac{1}{x} dx$, which is Exercise E.6 of Giordano and Nakanishi (2006). The MINITAB code for the calculation is shown in Appendix 15.9. Some results are shown in Table 3. We see that the simulation is not accurate and it converges very slowly toward the true value even with a large sample size. More efficient method is needed in this calculation using the Monte Carlo method.

5 Other comments on stochastic tools

The little book by Chorin and Hald (2006) tells an interesting story about some facets of the stochastic mathematics that are very popular in applied sciences:

- *The inner product and orhogonality of sets.* In a vector space V , vectors u and v are defined as *orthogonal* if their inner product (u, v) equals zero:

$$(u, v) = \sum_{i=1}^n u_i v_i = 0. \quad (24)$$

In Equation 24, u_i and v_i can be taken as the i th elements of the corresponding vectors. In a cartesian coordinate, suppose we choose two points, one located at somewhere on the x line, such as $(x_i, 0)$, and the other on the y line, denoted as $(0, y_i)$. It is apparent that their inner product is *zero*: signifying the fact that the x - y lines are *perpendicular*. Because of this property, any point on the x - y plane can be represented by a combination of points located on x and y axes. The fact that two vectors u_i and v_i in V are *orthogonal* might also be interpreted as having similar importance in defining any function within the set V .

- *The orthonormal basis and Fourier transform of functions.* A collection of the m vectors $\{u_i\}_{i=1}^m$ in a linear vector space S is called a *basis* of S if $\{u_i\}$ are linearly independent and any vector in S can be represented as linear combination of them. In an *orthonormal basis* $\{e_i\}_{i=1}^m$, the vectors are mutually orthogonal and each has unit length: that is, $(e_i, e_j) = \delta_{ij}$, with $\delta_{ij} = 1$ for $i = j$ and $\delta_{ij} = 0$ otherwise. This nice feature of orthonormal basis might be a factor that makes the mathematics of Fourier and wavelet transforms to be simple for wide applications. The functions $\tau^{-1/2} \exp(2\pi i k x / \tau)$ are an orthonormal basis on the interval $[-\tau/2, \tau/2]$. The Fourier transform is defined as:

$$\hat{f}(2\pi k/\tau) = \int_{-\tau/2}^{\tau/2} f(s) e^{-2\pi i k s/\tau} ds. \quad (25)$$

With $\tau \rightarrow \infty$ and k/τ replaced by the continuous variable t , Equation (25) becomes

$$\hat{f}(l) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(s) e^{-ils} ds, \quad (26)$$

where $l = 2\pi t$.

- *Bayes' theorem and conditional probability.* The Bayes' theorem provides an opportunity for estimating model parameters through the assimilation of new data. This framework sheds a light on proper understanding of some important data assimilation techniques, such as those based on the *Kalman filtering* (see Pages 89–92 of Charin and Hald (2006)). The following excerpts are from pages 38–42 of the above text. We will add some additional comments and analysis, so that the strength of the theorem becomes more evident.

The first form of the Bayes' theorem is stated as: Let A and B be two events with $P(A) \neq 0$ and $P(B) \neq 0$. Then,

$$P(A|B) = \frac{P(B|A)P(A)}{P(B)}. \quad (27)$$

The second form of the Bayes' theorem is stated by Chorin and Hald (2006) as: Let $Z = \{Z_j\}$, $j = 1, 2, \dots$, is a finite or countable partition of the sample space Ω , then for the probability $P(A)$ of an event A , we have

$$P(Z_j|A) = \frac{P(A|Z_j)P(Z_j)}{\sum_j P(A|Z_j)P(Z_j)}. \quad (28)$$

For the application of the second form of the Bayes' theorem, let's consider the sampling space Ω being divided into j disjoint sections, each with a probability. That means that we have a *prior* belief about the likeliness of occurrence of each of the partitioned sections in the *whole* set Ω . Now, this second form of the theorem can be used to update our belief about the probability of the event of section j of Ω to be happening (that is, Z_j) based on the result of our measurement data, e.g., that of event A . In other words, we will see how the probability of the event Z_j conditioned on event A can be changed by using information of A . Here is the example from Chorin and Hald (2006), pages 39-40:

Let η_1 and η_2 be two independent and identically distributed random variables with

$$\eta_1, \eta_2 = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{with probability } p \\ 0 & \text{with probability } 1 - p. \end{cases}$$

For the sum $\eta_1 + \eta_2$ we can deduce

$$\eta_1 + \eta_2 = \begin{cases} 2 & \text{with probability } p^2 \\ 1 & \text{with probability } 2p(1-p) \\ 0 & \text{with probability } (1-p)^2. \end{cases}$$

Suppose that before the experiment we thought that the parameter p had the value $p = 1/4$ with probability $1/4$ and the value $p = 1/2$ with probability $3/4$. This is the “prior distribution”. Now we make an experiment and find $\eta_1 + \eta_2 = 1$. We can use Equation 28 to see how the experiment affects our belief about the distribution of parameter p . To do that, let A be the event that $\eta_1 + \eta_2 = 1$, Z_1 be the event that the value of p is $1/4$ (which has a prior probability of $1/4$) and let Z_2 be the event that $p = 1/2$ (which has a prior probability of $3/4$). Then, using Equation 28 we find that $P(Z_1|A) = \frac{1}{5}$. This *posterior* probability for Z_1 is lower than its prior, which is $\frac{1}{4}$. This means that our belief that $p = 1/4$ is weakened in light of one experimental result! Actually, if we use this newly obtained (posterior) probability ($1/5$) as the new prior, and conduct a new observation which also yields $\eta_1 + \eta_2 = 1$, then our belief will further be weakened. After about 12 runs of new experiment (all having in the same result: $\eta_1 + \eta_2 = 1$), the final posterior probability is less than 0.01! That means repeatedly observing this same result will eventually lead us to believe that the correct value of p is almost $1/2$, instead of $1/4$. The MINITAB code for doing this simulation is shown in Appendix 15.10 and the result is shown in Table 4. To understand this result, let’s recall how the sampling space Ω is partitioned (Table 5). It is partitioned only in two segments: Z_1 and Z_2 . Z_1 means p is lower ($1/4$) while Z_2 means a higher p value ($1/2$). Their respective probabilities ($1/4$ vs. $3/4$) suggest that $p = 1/2$ is more likely, if we don’t consider any new data. Now the repeated occurring of event $\eta_1 + \eta_2 = 1$ suggests that the probability of this event needs to be increased. Because there are only two choices for the value of p (either $1/4$ or $1/2$). Given $6/16 < 1/2$, we are forced to prefer $p = 1/2$ (over $p = 1/4$) in order to be compatible with the measurement (repeated occurrence of $\eta_1 + \eta_2 = 1$).

Now, if we assume our measurements contain a repeated occurrence of $\eta_1 + \eta_2 = 2$ instead, then how would our posterior probability of $P(Z_1|A)$ end up with, if all other aspects of the problem remain unchanged? The result is shown in Table 6¹¹. We see that under such a situation, the posterior probability of $P(Z_1|A)$ also decreases, but with a fast speed (becoming less than 0.01 after only two iterations). This can be interpreted similarly as when A is $\eta_1 + \eta_2 = 1$, but here because $1/16 \ll 1/4$, each measurement has a more significant effect.

Finally, let’s consider the case when A is defined as the event $\eta_1 + \eta_2 = 0$. This time, the repeated occurrence of $\eta_1 + \eta_2 = 0$ suggests an increase of p , but it is already true that $9/16 > 1/4$, so the partition of $p = 1/4$ is preferred. We can predict that after

¹¹The MINITAB code of Appendix 15.10 will need to be modified for these two lines: *let k1 = 1/16 # P(A|Z1)* and *let k2 = 9/16 # P(A|Z2)*.

Table 4: The prior and posterior probabilities for the event Z_1 conditioned on the event A , which is defined as $\eta_1 + \eta_2 = 1$.

<i>Prior</i>	<i>Posterior</i>
0.2500	0.2000
0.2000	0.1579
0.1579	0.1233
0.1233	0.0954
0.0954	0.0733
0.0733	0.056
0.056	0.0426
0.0426	0.0323
0.0323	0.0244
0.0244	0.0184
0.0184	0.0139
0.0139	0.0104
0.0104	0.0079

Table 5: Probabilities of the events $\eta_1 + \eta_2$ for each of the two partitions of the sampling space Ω : $Z_1 : p = 1/4$ with a probability of $1/4$ and $Z_2 : p = 1/2$ with a probability of $3/4$.

$\eta_1 + \eta_2$	$p(p = 1/4)$	$p(p = 1/2)$
2	1/16	1/4
1	6/16	1/2
0	9/16	1/4

a few iterations, the posterior probability of $P(Z_1|A)$ will approach 1.0, and indeed it does, as indicated in Table 7¹².

- *Data assimilation.* We summarize the treatment of Charin and Hald (2006) on this topic (pages 89–92) in the following. Their treatment of this method is slightly different from those that are in some typical engineering books.

“The use of data together with a model to assess the current state of a system and/or to make predictions is called ‘data assimilation’ and the algorithms for doing that is called ‘filters’.” There are two steps for conducting data assimilation:

1. State extrapolation. Let P_i be the probability density of x up to time $i\delta$. To find the probability density of x at times $i\delta < x < (i + 1)\delta$ (before any new observations come in), one can sample P_i , evolve the samples independently by

$$dx = f(x, t)dt + g(x, t)d\omega, \tag{29}$$

¹²The MINITAB code for this problem (assuming A is defined as $\eta_1 + \eta_2 = 0$) involves modifications of the following two lines: *let k1 = 9/16 ‡ P(A|Z₁)* and *let k2 = 1/16 ‡ P(A|Z₂)*.

Table 6: The prior and posterior probabilities for the event Z_1 conditioned on the event A , which is defined as $\eta_1 + \eta_2 = 2$.

<i>Prior</i>	<i>Posterior</i>
0.2500	0.0357
0.0357	0.0041

Table 7: The prior and posterior probabilities for the event Z_1 conditioned on the event A , which is defined as $\eta_1 + \eta_2 = 0$.

<i>Prior</i>	<i>Posterior</i>
0.2500	0.7500
0.7500	0.9643
0.9643	0.9959

where $x = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$ is an n -dimensional vector, $d\omega$ is an n -dimensional *Brownian motion* encapsulating all that is unknown in this model. The initial state $x(0)$ is assumed given and may be random as well. Whenever needed, some method (such as parametric estimation) may be used to reconstruct a density.

2. State update. This is to modify the density at time $(i + 1)\delta$ when new data must be taken into account, and it is done through

$$P(x|\bar{y}_{i+1}) = \frac{P(y_{i+1}|x(t))P(x|\bar{y}_i)}{\int P(y_{i+1}|x)P(x|\bar{y}_i)dx}, \quad (30)$$

where $P(x|\bar{y}_i)$ is the probability density determined from Equation 29 taking into account the data up to and including time $i\delta$ but not the data at time $(i + 1)\delta$, $P(y_{i+1}|x(t))$ is the probability of finding the data if one knows the value $x((i + 1)\delta)$ of the unknown data x , which can be found from the observation equation

$$y_i = h(x_i, t_i) + GW_i, \quad (31)$$

where h is a k -dimensional vector, and in principle $k \leq n$, h is a non-linear function, G is a diagonal matrix with non-zero diagonal terms, $x_i = x(i\delta)$, and W_i is a vector whose components are independent Gaussian variables of $N(0,1)$, also independent of the Brownian motion. The integral in the denominator of Equation 30 is needed to normalize the probabilities. Here $P(x|\bar{y}_i)$ is the prior and $P(x|\bar{y}_{i+1})$ is the posterior.

Evaluate the formula of Equation 30 as follows. (1) Find n samples of P_i and evolve them using Equation 29. (2) Reconstruct the density from the positions of these samples after evolution, and regard it as the prior density. (3) Use the new information at time $(i + 1)\delta$ to assign a probability to each new sample position according to Equation 31 and

$$P(s_j < x_j \leq s_j + ds_j) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi g_{jj}^2}} \exp\left(-\frac{(s_j - h_j(x, t))^2}{2g_{jj}^2}\right) ds_j, \quad (32)$$

where g_{jj} is a diagonal entry of matrix G .

6 State estimation through filtering

What natural scientists call “data assimilation” seems to often be referred to as “state estimation” in engineering literature, such as in Simon (2006). The latter emphasizes the dynamics of the system and bears more connections with control theory¹³, while the former use seems to place the emphasis on experimental data and simulation. While the most explored method of this kind may be the technique of *Kalman filtering*, the central idea perhaps can be best illustrated through a later development called “particle filtering”, a data assimilation method closely associated with the Bayesian state estimation, as vividly shown in Chapter 15 of Simon (2006) (pages 461–468). Through Simon’s derivation of the Bayesian state estimation and particle filtering, we will have a better understand of some of the rather condensed material of the same topic (Data assimilation) in Chorin and Hald (2006). In particular, we will have fuller understanding of components of Equation 30.

6.1 Bayesian state estimator

1. Assume we have a non-linear system described by equations

$$\begin{aligned} x_{k+1} &= f_k(x_k, w_k) \\ y_k &= h_k(x_k, v_k), \end{aligned} \quad (33)$$

where $\{w_k\}$ and $\{v_k\}$ are vectors describing system noise and measurement noise and $f(\cdot)$ and $h(\cdot)$ are time-varying nonlinear equations. Both noise vectors are independent, white processes with known probability density functions (pdf’s)¹⁴. The goal of Bayesian estimation is to find the conditional pdf of x_k , $p(x_k|(y_1, y_2, \dots, y_k)) = p(x_k|Y_k)$, based on observed measurements y_1, y_2, \dots, y_k .

2. The pdf of the initial state, $p(x_0)$, is assumed to be known, and the initial estimator is

$$p(x_0|Y_0) = p(x_0). \quad (34)$$

here Y_0 means non-measurement; nothing is measured but its use is just for mathematical completeness.

¹³As illustrated in A. Gelb. et al. 1974. Applied Optimal estimation. MIT Press, Cambridge, Massachusetts.

¹⁴If a random variable has a known pdf, some important statistical measures, such as expected values (means) and variances, usually can be obtained readily.

3. For times of $k = 1, 2, \dots$, we do the following computation:

(a) Compute the *a priori* pdf for x_k as

$$p(x_k|Y_{k-1}) = \int p(x_k|x_{k-1})p(x_{k-1}|Y_{k-1})dx_{k-1}, \quad (35)$$

where $p(x_k|x_{k-1})$ is the pdf of x_k given x_{k-1} and $p(x_{k-1}|Y_{k-1})$ is the pdf of x_{k-1} given all the previous system states prior to x_k . It is called “*a priori*” because this pdf of x_k takes into consideration all the past states, but does not consider the current state, x_k . This pdf can be obtained using the system function $x_{k+1} = f_k(x_k, w_k)$; it is the pdf of w_k being passed through system function $f(\cdot)$ considering the current system state x_k (assumed to be known). Depending on the nature of the pdf of w_k , we might use various methods for transforming a random variable (vector) to obtain this conditional pdf ($p(x_k|x_{k-1})$)¹⁵. The pdf $p(x_{k-1}|Y_{k-1})$ can be obtained iteratively considering the known initial pdf $p(x_0|Y_0) = p(x_0)$. The integral at the right-hand side of Equation 35 is a result of computing the *marginal pdf* (we will come back to this point shortly).

(b) Compute the *a posteriori* pdf for x_k as

$$p(x_k|Y_k) = \frac{p(y_k|x_k)p(x_k|Y_{k-1})}{\int p(y_k|x_k)p(x_k|Y_{k-1})dx_k}, \quad (36)$$

where $p(x_k|Y_{k-1})$ is the prior pdf as in Equation 35 and $p(y_k|x_k)$ is the likelihood of obtaining observation y_k with known system state at time k , x_k . Equation 36 is identical to Equation 30 (except for differences in notation), and we see the the posterior pdf is obtained using information of prior pdf, current observation, current system state, as well as system and measurement functions. As shown in the discussion of Equation 30, the formula of posterior pdf may be evaluated numerically, such as using *particle filtering* when the system and measurement functions are highly non-linear. Some other filtering methods, such as the *ensemble Kalman filtering*, or *extended Kalman filtering*, may be useful with non-linear system and measurement functions. However, if the system and measurement functions are *linear*, then the standard *Kalman filtering* is the most efficient method to use.

6.2 The derivations of the prior and posterior pdf’s

Here we summarize some key steps in the derivation of $p(x_k|Y_{k-1})$ and $p(x_k|Y_k)$. This subsection is based on Chapter 15 of Simon (2006). First, we review two important concepts on the properties of probability density functions.

- *The marginal pdf.* This is reviewed on page 61 of Simon (2006). Consider two independent random variables x and y . The marginal probability distribution functions

¹⁵See pages 59–60 of Simon (2006) for an introduction of the transformation of random variables.

(PDF's) can be obtained from the joint PDF's as:

$$\begin{aligned} F(x, \infty) &= F(x) \\ F(\infty, y) &= F(y). \end{aligned} \tag{37}$$

Likewise, the marginal pdf's can be obtained as

$$\begin{aligned} f(x) &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(x, y) dy \\ f(y) &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(x, y) dx. \end{aligned} \tag{38}$$

- *The Chapman-Kolmogorov equation on the relation among conditional pdf, joint pdf, and marginal pdf.* This is reviewed on page 54 of Simon (2006). For two random variables X_1 and X_2 , according to the Bayes' the conditional pdf $f_{X_1|X_2}(x_1|x_2)$ can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} f_{X_1|X_2}(x_1|x_2) &= P[(X_1 \leq x_1)|(X_2 = x_2)] \\ &= \frac{f_{X_1, X_2}(x_1, x_2)}{f_{X_2}(x_2)}, \end{aligned} \tag{39}$$

which is a direct result of the definition of the conditional probability

$$P(A|B) = \frac{P(A, B)}{P(B)}, \tag{40}$$

as briefly reviewed in page 51 of Simon (2006). Now suppose we have three random variables X_1 , X_2 and X_3 , and we consider the product of the following two conditional pdf's:

$$\begin{aligned} f[x_1|(x_2, x_3)]f(x_2|x_3) &= \frac{f(x_1, x_2, x_3)}{f(x_2, x_3)} \frac{f(x_2, x_3)}{f(x_3)} \\ &= \frac{f(x_1, x_2, x_3)}{f(x_3)} \\ &= f[(x_1, x_2)|x_3]. \end{aligned} \tag{41}$$

This is called the Chapman-Kolmogorov equation, and here we dropped the random variables X_1, \dots , but just used their realizations x_1, \dots , to simplify the representation. This equation is important because it gives exact relation among conditional probabilities (here they are $f[x_1|(x_2, x_3)]$ and $f(x_2|x_3)$), joint probability (here it is $f(x_1, x_2, x_3)$) and marginal probability (here it is $f(x_3)$). It is fundamental to Bayesian state estimation.

To derive Equation 35, we first use formula of the marginal pdf (Equation 38) to express $p(x_k|Y_{k-1})$ into an integral

$$p(x_k|Y_{k-1}) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} p[(x_k, x_{k-1})|Y_{k-1}] dx_{k-1}. \tag{42}$$

The integrand of the above equation is a conditional joint pdf (of x_k and x_{k-1}), and it can be expanded as the product of two conditional pdf's according to Equation 41 (we drop the infinity signs for simplicity):

$$p(x_k|Y_{k-1}) = \int p[x_k|(x_{k-1}, Y_{k-1})]p(x_{k-1}|Y_{k-1})dx_{k-1}. \quad (43)$$

Now comparing Equations 43 and 35, we note if we can show

$$p[x_k|(x_{k-1}, Y_{k-1})] = p(x_k|x_{k-1}), \quad (44)$$

then the derivation of the prior pdf (Equation 35) is completed. The fact that the system state x_k at time k is *entirely* determined by x_{k-1} and w_{k-1} suggests that Equation 44 does hold. As a result, Equation 35 also holds.

Now let's consider the derivation of Equation 36. It is really not straight forward to figure out the method of derivation just by looking at this equation, though from our previous of experience of deriving the prior pdf, it is likely that the denominator may be obtained by expressing some marginal pdf by an integral of some joint pdf¹⁶. The following is a derivation due to Simon (2006), pages 464–465.

The posterior pdf for x_k can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} p(x_k|Y_k) &= \frac{p(Y_k|x_k)}{p(Y_k)}p(x_k) \\ &= \frac{p[(y_k, Y_{k-1})|x_k]}{p(y_k, Y_{k-1})} \frac{p(x_k|Y_{k-1})p(Y_{k-1})}{p(Y_{k-1}|x_k)}. \end{aligned} \quad (45)$$

It should be noted that the Bayes' rule was used for the first step. Then, the event (Y_k) is the same as event (y_k, Y_{k-1}). Also, the second fraction of the second line of Equation 45 actually is due to using of the Bayes' rule on $p(x_k|Y_{k-1})$ and solving for $p(x_k)$. Now, in Equation 45, we can express the two conditional pdf's $p[(y_k, Y_{k-1})|x_k]$ and $p(x_k|Y_{k-1})$ as ratios of a joint pdf and a marginal pdf according to Equation 41, but leave the other conditional pdf $p(Y_{k-1}|x_k)$ not changed. We get the following form

$$p(x_k|Y_k) = \frac{p(x_k, y_k, Y_{k-1})}{p(x_k)p(y_k, Y_{k-1})} \frac{p(x_k, Y_{k-1})p(Y_{k-1})}{p(Y_{k-1})p(Y_{k-1}|x_k)}. \quad (46)$$

Next step, Simon (2006) multiplied both the numerator and denominator of the above equation by $p(x_k, y_k)$. But it seems that this multiplication is not necessary, because we can simply express the three joint pdf's by their corresponding conditional pdf's and marginal pdf's (in Equation 46) and obtain the following result:

$$p(x_k|Y_k) = \frac{p[Y_{k-1}|(x_k, y_k)]p(y_k|x_k)p(x_k|Y_{k-1})}{p(y_k|Y_{k-1})p(Y_{k-1}|x_k)}. \quad (47)$$

¹⁶At this point, I want to remind myself that the capital letter Y as in $p(x_k|Y_k)$ is not about name of a random variable, instead it refers to a vector of all the observations including and prior to time k

Now Simon (2006) used an important relation $p[Y_{k-1}|(x_k, y_k)] = p(Y_{k-1}|x_k)$ (because “ y_k is a function of x_k ”) to simplify the above equation as

$$p(x_k|Y_k) = \frac{p(y_k|x_k)p(x_k|Y_{k-1})}{p(y_k|Y_{k-1})}. \quad (48)$$

We see that the numerator of Equation 48 is the same as Equation 36. If we can show that the denominator of 48 also equals the denominator of Equation 36, then our derivation of the posterior pdf is completed. Actually, it is, as shown in the following equation:

$$\begin{aligned} p(y_k|Y_{k-1}) &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} p[(y_k, x_k)|Y_{k-1}]dx_k \\ &= \int p[y_k|(x_k, Y_{k-1})]p(x_k|Y_{k-1})dx_k \\ &= \int p(y_k|x_k)p(x_k|Y_{k-1})dx_k. \end{aligned} \quad (49)$$

The first two lines of the above equation are due to the same logic as has been used for deriving the prior pdf (Equations 42 and 43). The third line of Equation 49 is due to the fact that “ y_k is completely determined by x_k and v_k , so $p[y_k|(x_k, Y_{k-1})] = p(y_k|x_k)$ ” (page 465 of Simon (2006)).

6.3 Particle filtering for numerical Bayesian estimation

Particle filter¹⁷ was designed to numerically implement the pdf of Equation 36 (Simon, 2006, pages 466–469). The basic idea is (1) to use the initial pdf $p(x_0)$ for state x_0 at time $k = 0$ to randomly generate an *ensemble* of states (particles) capturing both the mean and covariance of system states; (2) to evolve the randomly generated particles based on system equation (first of Equation 33); and (3) to update the particles based on new measurement and measurement equation (second of Equation 33).

1. *Particle initializing* As pdf of the initial state $p(x_0)$ is assumed to be known, it is possible to use standard method to randomly generate N state vectors (or particles) based on this known pdf. These particles are denoted as $x_{0,i}^+$, for $i = 1, \dots, N$. The plus sign suggests the system state has been updated based on information of the current “data” x_0 .
2. *Particle evolving* At each time step $k = 1, 2, \dots$, we propagate the system state according to the system equation $f(\cdot)$:

$$x_{k,i}^- = f_{k-1}(x_{k-1,i}^+, w_{k-1}^i), \quad (50)$$

where w_{k-1}^i is the i th ($i=1,2,\dots,N$) system noise vector at the previous time step $k - 1$, and $x_{k,i}^-$ is the calculated system state at the current time k considering all the measurements prior to time k (indicated with a minus sign).

¹⁷It is also referred to as: bootstrap filter, condensation algorithm, interesting particle approximation, Monte Carlo filter, sequential importance sampling, sequential Monte Carlo filter.

3. *Particle updating* This update step can further be split into two sub-steps:

- (a) *Computing the relative likelihood for each of the N particles* This is to evaluate the conditional pdf $p(y_k|x_{k,i}^-)$, giving the non-linear measurement equation and the pdf of measurement noise. For the measurement equation $y_k = h(x_k, v_k)$, if we can solve for v_k so as to obtain $v_k = h'(y_k, x_k)$, then, because the pdf of v_k is known, the conditional likelihood $p(y_k|x_{k,i}^-)$ can be obtained as $p((y_k = y^*)|(x_k = x_{k,i}^-)) = p(v_k = h'(y_k, x_{k,i}^-))$ ¹⁸. We can normalize the N likelihoods $q_i = p(y_k|x_{k,i}^-)$, $i = 1, \dots, N$, so that the sum of all the likelihoods equals one:

$$q_i = \frac{q_i}{\sum_{j=1}^N q_j}. \quad (51)$$

- (b) *Resampling from the computed likelihoods* Next, we resample from the computed relative likelihoods to generate our posterior particle $x_{k,i}^+$ with an ensemble pdf tending to $p(x_k|y_k)$, the posterior pdf that we want to evaluate¹⁹. Different methods of resampling, such as MCMC (Markov chain Monte Carlo), can be used to obtain the posterior pdf. Simon (2006) cited a direct method due to (Ristic et al., 2004)²⁰:

- i. Generate a random number r that is uniformly distributed on $[0, 1]$.
- ii. Start a DO LOOP from 1 to N with index i . Accumulate the likelihoods q_i into a sum, one at a time, until at the j th particle when the sum is greater than or equal to r . Then quit the DO LOOP and let $x_{k,i}^+ = x_{k,j}^-$.

The above algorithm was proved by Ristic et al. (2004).

7 Limit and continuation

To find the limit of indeterminate form of $\frac{\infty}{\infty}$, sometimes L'Hôpital's rule does not work. For example, the limit

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} \ln \frac{\sqrt{5}x}{\sqrt{1+4x^2}} \quad (52)$$

as

¹⁸See Simon (2006) page 466 for an example.

¹⁹This refers to Equation 36, but here instead of writing Y_k we write y_k , because we evaluate this pdf numerically so that each of the measurement, y_1, y_2, \dots, y_k , is taken into consideration one by one through particle evolving and updating steps as discussed in this section.

²⁰B. Ristic, S. Arulampalam, and N. Gordon. Beyond the Kalman Filter: Particle Filters for Tracking Applications. Artech House, Norwell, Massachusetts

$$\begin{aligned}
\lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} \ln \frac{\sqrt{5}x}{\sqrt{1+4x^2}} &= \lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} \ln \frac{\sqrt{5}}{\sqrt{\frac{1+4x^2}{x^2}}} \\
&= \lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} \ln \frac{\sqrt{5}}{\sqrt{\frac{1}{x^2} + 4}} \\
&= \lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} \ln \sqrt{\frac{5}{4}} \\
&= \frac{1}{2} \ln \frac{5}{4}.
\end{aligned} \tag{53}$$

The key is to observe that $x = \sqrt{x^2}$.

Now look at this limit problem:

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{1 - \cos x}{x^3}. \tag{54}$$

Note that at $x = 0$ both the numerator and denominator approach zero and the limit appears to be in the indeterminate form of $\frac{0}{0}$. Let's try to do some transformation on $\cos x$ and consider the case when x approaches 0 from the right (positive) side of the x axis:

$$\begin{aligned}
\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{1 - \cos x}{x^3} &= \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{(1 - \cos x)(1 + \cos x)}{x^3(1 + \cos x)} \\
&= \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{(1 - \cos^2 x)}{x^3(1 + \cos x)} \\
&= \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{\sin^2 x}{x^3(1 + \cos x)} \\
&= \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{\sin^2 x}{x^2} \cdot \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{1}{x(1 + \cos x)} \\
&= \left[\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{\sin x}{x} \right]^2 \cdot \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{1}{x} \cdot \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{1}{(1 + \cos x)} \\
&= 1^2 \cdot \infty \cdot \frac{1}{2} \\
&= \infty.
\end{aligned} \tag{55}$$

When x approaches 0 from the left (negative) side of the x axis, Equation 54 will approach $-\infty$. As a result, Equation 54 does not have a limit when $x \rightarrow 0$ (See Figure 1).

The above analysis indicates that the numerator of Equation 54 approaches 0 at a **much lower speed** than does the denominator (from the right or left side of the origin). This can be verified by plotting functions $y = 1 - \cos x$ and $y = x^3$ using a calculator (see Figure 2).

Figure 1: Graphs of $y = \frac{1-\cos x}{x^3}$. It shows that y approaches $+\infty$ when x approaches 0 from right side, and $-\infty$ when x approaches 0 from left side.

8 Numerical evaluation of definite integrals

Hanna and Hanna²¹ provided a simple but effective method to approximately evaluate definite integrals defined either by analytical functions or by discrete data. This is *trapezoidal rule with Richardson extrapolation*. First we recall the Euler-Maclaurin summation formula for definite integral, $\int_a^b f(x) dt$.

$$\int_a^b f(x) dt = h \left[\frac{f(a)}{2} + f(a+h) + f(a+2h) + \dots + f(b-h) + \frac{f(b)}{2} \right] - \frac{h^2[f'(b) - f'(a)]}{12} + \frac{h^4[f'''(b) - f'''(a)]}{720} - \frac{h^6[f^{(5)}(b) - f^{(5)}(a)]}{30240} + R \quad (56)$$

Here the integration domain is equally divided into m segments and the length of each segment is h . If we denote the value of the integral as I ($I = \int_a^b f(x) dt$), the first term in Eq.(56) as $A(h)$, also let $K_1 = -[f'(b) - f'(a)]/12$, $K_2 = [f'''(b) - f'''(a)]/720$, and $K_3 = -[f^{(5)}(b) - f^{(5)}(a)]/30240$, then we have the following equation,

²¹Hanna O.T and Hanna W.F., 1999. An Introduction to Numerical Methods using True Basic. True Basic Inc., West Lebanon, NH, USA

Figure 2: Graphs of $y = 1 - \cos x$ (top panel) and $y = x^3$ (bottom panel) on a very narrow domain enclosing 0. Note the differences in the y (vertical) axis scale for two graphs.

$$I = A(h) + K_1h^2 + K_2h^4 + K_3h^6 + R \quad (57)$$

For sufficiently small h , the terms in the right-hand side of Eq.(57) decrease with the increase of the powers of h , e.g., the value of the integral is primarily determined by the leading term, $A(h)$, and the later terms (K_2h^4, K_3h^6, R) and their sum is comparably small and can be denoted as $O(h^4)$. If, for small h , $O(h^4)$ is omitted, the value of the integral can be approximated by

$$I = A(h) + K_1h^2 + O(h^4), \quad h \rightarrow 0 \quad (58)$$

Here in Eq.(58), because $A(h)$ is determined with the integrand evaluated at h , there left 2 unknowns, I , and K_1 . These could be obtained by evaluating Eq.(58) twice: once as it stands as in Eq.(58), and once using $h/2$.

$$I = A(h/2) + K_1(h/2)^2 + O(h^4), \quad h \rightarrow 0 \quad (59)$$

Thus $K_1(h/2)^2$ in Eq.(59) can be obtained as,

$$K_1(h/2)^2 = \frac{A(h/2) - A(h)}{2^2 - 1} \quad (60)$$

Substituting Eq.(60) into Eq.(59), we have

$$I = A(h/2) + \frac{A(h/2) - A(h)}{2^2 - 1} + O(h^4) \quad (61)$$

Because the error of non-extrapolated trapezoidal rule is in the $O(h^2)$ term, we see that using the once Richardson extrapolation, the error is in the $O(h^4)$ term, which is generally smaller than the non-extrapolated $O(h^2)$ error. Also, Eq.(60) can be used as a *conservative estimate* of the true error incurred in the once extrapolated method, which is in the $O(h^4)$ term. By saying *conservative*, we mean the true error is generally bounded within the conservative estimation.

Eq.(61) is the basic equation for the numerical quadrature²² of definite integrals using the trapezoidal rule with once-Richardson extrapolation. In computer it is convenient to do the *repeated* extrapolation, for example we can do the twice-extrapolation by evaluating not only $A(h), A(h/2)$, but also $A(h/4)$. The normalized ratio between the two estimates of the once-extrapolated error, e.g., K_1h^2 , can be used to indicate if the estimated *conservative* error is actually larger than the true error. For the first extrapolation, K_1h^2 is estimated as $K_1h^2 = [A(h/2) - A(h)]/(2^2 - 1)$; for the second extrapolation, K_1h^2 is estimated as $K_1h^2 = 4[A(h/4) - A(h/2)]/(2^2 - 1)$. *When their ratio ranges between 0.8 and 1.2, we are confidently sure that the estimated conservative error is actually bounding the true error.*

In the above discussion, the evaluation of $A(h)$ is done with successively increments decreased by a factor of $1/2$ (0.5). However, other factors that lies between 0 and 1 can be used in the Richardson extrapolation.

²²e.g., numerical evaluation of definite integrals, as used here.

Also, in Eq.(58), the exponent of h may not be 2, but can be unknown. In this case experimental determination of this exponent is necessary. In this case, Eq.(60) becomes

$$K_1(h/2)^p = \frac{A(h/2) - A(h)}{2^p - 1} \quad (62)$$

By evaluating Eq.(62) twice, once using h and once using $h/2$, and dividing the two resultant equations, we can obtain

$$2^p = \frac{A(h/2) - A(h)}{A(h/4) - A(h/2)} \quad (63)$$

Taking natural logarithms, we have,

$$p = \ln\left[\frac{A(h/2) - A(h)}{A(h/4) - A(h/2)}\right] / \ln 2 \quad (64)$$

The program TBTRQUAD (Hanna and Hanna, 1999) can be used to some analytically defined integrals, provided that the integrand *should not have an unbounded derivatives within the integration domain*. Frequently, this happens when there is a *fractional power in a range including zero* in the integrand function. In this situation, a change of variable may be used to resolve the difficulty. An examples are given in Exercise 9.3, in which the integral $I = \int_0^1 e^{-t}/(1+t^{1/2}) dt$ contains a fractional power near $t = 0$. When such problems exist, the *Ratio* in program TBTRQUAD is about 0.6, which is out of the desired range of $0.8 < Ratio < 1.2$. A change of variable using $u = t^{1/2}$ can help. This and similar problems are important in correctly using this methods. Other examples or discussions are given in Hanna and Sandall (1995), page 226-229.

When the integrand is defined by discrete data, we have to use hand calculation to obtain the approximated values of integration and related errors. An once-extrapolated example is given in the current book on page 157, and a twice-extrapolated example is given in Hanna and Sandall (1995), page 231. Although, as indicated in the latter example, the *Ratio* indicator is not satisfactory because of the sparse data, but the result is correct to 3 decimal points. The method reviewed here is totally deterministic. If the data is “contaminated” with experimental error, it might be better to first use some kind of least squares approximation to smooth the data.

9 Review of differential equations

9.1 Simple differential equations: Howard Anton 3rd ed.

1. First order separable equations. If ODE can be arranged as the form:

$$\frac{dy}{dx} = \frac{g(x)}{h(y)} \quad (65)$$

Then, rewrite to have

$$h(y)dy = g(x)dx \quad (66)$$

Integrating both sides,

$$\int h(y) dy = \int g(x) dx \quad (67)$$

2. First order linear equations. A first order equation is called *linear* if it is expressible in the form

$$\frac{dy}{dx} + p(x)y = q(x) \quad (68)$$

where $p(x)$ and $q(x)$ may not be constant. To solve this equation, (1) calculate $\rho = e^{\int p(x)dx}$ (integrating factor); (2) multiply both sides of (68) by ρ to have $\frac{d}{dx}(\rho y) = \rho q(x)$; (3) integrating, and add constant, to obtain $y = \frac{1}{\rho}[\int q(x) dx] + C$. Applications include

$$\begin{aligned} \text{exponential growth, } \frac{dy}{dx} &= ky, \text{ doubling time } T = \frac{1}{k} \ln 2 \\ \text{exponential decay, } \frac{dy}{dx} &= -ky, \text{ halving time } T = -\frac{1}{k} \ln 2. \end{aligned}$$

3. Homogeneous equations (2nd order).

$$y'' + py' + qy = r(x) \quad (69)$$

where $p, q = \text{constant}$, $r(x) = 0$.

The general solution depends on the solution of the auxiliary equation, $m^2 + pm + q = 0$

$$m_1 = \frac{-p + \sqrt{p^2 - 4q}}{2} \quad (70)$$

$$m_2 = \frac{-p - \sqrt{p^2 - 4q}}{2} \quad (71)$$

(a) if auxiliary equation has distinctive real roots, m_1, m_2 , the general solution of $y'' + py'' + q = 0$ is $y(x) = c_1 e^{m_1 x} + c_2 e^{m_2 x}$.

(b) if the auxiliary equation has identical roots, $m_1 = m_2 = m$, the general solution of $y'' + py'' + q = 0$ is, $y(x) = c_1 e^{mx} + c_2 x e^{mx}$.

(c) if the auxiliary equation has complex roots, $m_1 = a + bi, m_2 = a - bi$, the general solution of $y'' + py'' + q = 0$ is $y(x) = e^{ax}(c_1 \cos bx + c_2 \sin bx)$.

4. For non-homogeneous equation (2nd order).

$$y'' + py' + qy = r(x) \quad (72)$$

where $p, q = \text{constant}$, and $r(x) \neq 0$.

The general solution is

$$y(x) = y_c(x) + y_p(x) \quad (73)$$

where $y_c(x) = c_1y_1(x) + c_2y_2(x)$ is the general solution of the complimentary equation $y'' + py' + q = 0$, and $y_p(x)$ is a particular solution of $y'' + py' + q = r(x)$.

The strategy of finding $y_p(x)$ is by guessing and substituting the general solution into original ODE to see if it really is a solution. There are 3 situations,

(a) If $r(x) = Ke^{ax}$, first guess $y_p(x) = A_1e^{ax}$, but if A_1e^{ax} is a solution of the complimentary equation, use $y_p(x) = A_1xe^{ax}$.

(b) If $r(x) = a_0 + a_1x + \dots + a_nx^n$, first guess $y_p(x) = A_0 + A_1x + A_nx^n$. If any one term is solution to the complimentary equation, multiply x to $y_p(x)$, thus, $y_p(x) = x(A_0 + A_1x + A_nx^n)$.

(c) If $r(x) = a_1 \sin bx + a_2 \cos bx$, first guess $y_p(x) = A_1 \sin bx + A_2 \cos bx$. If any term is a solution of the complimentary equation, multiply $y_p(x)$ by x , thus $y_p(x) = x(A_1 \sin bx + A_2 \cos bx)$.

5. Using variation of parameters for non-homogeneous equations when guessing is not successful (type 4). For equation

$$y'' + py' + qy = r(x) \tag{74}$$

first the general solution of the complimentary equation $y'' + py' + qy = 0$ is $y_c(x) = c_1y_1(x) + c_2y_2(x)$. If we could find $u(x)$ and $v(x)$, so that

$$y_p(x) = u(x)y_1(x) + v(x)y_2(x) \tag{75}$$

is a particular solution to (74), but certainly $y_p(x)$ is not a solution to the complimentary equation. The general solution of (74) is $y(x) = y_c(x) + y_p(x)$. We will see what $u(x)$ and $v(x)$ must be, if $y_p(x) = uy_1(x) + vy_2(x)$ is a solution to (74). Differentiate (75), we have

$$y'_p(x) = uy'_1(x) + u'y_1(x) + vy'_2(x) + v'y_2(x) \tag{76}$$

We are now solving $u(x)$ and $v(x)$ and we want to get $y''_p(x)$, to simply u and v . We demand that

$$u'y_1(x) + v'y_2(x) = 0 \tag{77}$$

Now (76) becomes,

$$y'_p(x) = uy'_1(x) + vy'_2(x) \tag{78}$$

Differentiate (78) with respect to x , we have

$$y''_p(x) = uy''_1(x) + u'y'_1(x) + vy''_2(x) + v'y'_2(x) \tag{79}$$

Now substitute (75),(78) and(79) into (74), so doing because now we assume $y_p(x)$ is a solution to (74),

$$\overbrace{uy_1''(x) + u'y_1'(x) + vy_2''(x) + v'y_2'(x)} + \overbrace{py_1'(x) + pv'y_2'(x)} + \underbrace{qy_1(x) + qv'y_2(x)} = r(x) \quad (80)$$

Rearrange we have,

$$u[y_1''(x) + py_1'(x) + qy_1(x)] + v[y_2''(x) + py_2'(x) + qy_2(x)] + u'y_1'(x) + v'y_2'(x) = r(x) \quad (81)$$

Because $y_1(x)$ and $y_2(x)$ are solutions to equation $y'' + py' + qy = 0$, so that, $y_1''(x) + py_1'(x) + qy_1(x) = 0$ and $y_2''(x) + py_2'(x) + qy_2(x) = 0$, (80) becomes $u'y_1'(x) + v'y_2'(x) = r(x)$. To this point, we see that if $y_p(x) = uy_1(x) + vy_2(x)$ is a solution to (74), then the following two equations must be satisfied simultaneously,

$$u'y_1(x) + v'y_2(x) = 0 \quad (82)$$

$$u'y_1'(x) + v'y_2'(x) = r(x) \quad (83)$$

Now regarding u' and v' as variables, we can obtain u' , v' according to the Crame Rule,

$$u' = \frac{\begin{vmatrix} 0 & y_2(x) \\ r(x) & y_2'(x) \end{vmatrix}}{\begin{vmatrix} y_1(x) & y_2(x) \\ y_1'(x) & y_2'(x) \end{vmatrix}} \quad (84)$$

$$v' = \frac{\begin{vmatrix} y_1(x) & 0 \\ y_1'(x) & r(x) \end{vmatrix}}{\begin{vmatrix} y_1(x) & y_2(x) \\ y_1'(x) & y_2'(x) \end{vmatrix}} \quad (85)$$

Integrate, we can find expressions of u and v , without constants, so the general solution of (74) becomes,

$$\begin{aligned} y(x) &= y_c(x) + y_p(x) \\ &= C_1y_1(x) + C_2y_2(x) + uy_1(x) + vy_2(x) \\ &= C_1y_1(x) + C_2y_2(x) + u(x)y_1(x) + v(x)y_2(x) \end{aligned} \quad (86)$$

See text by Howard Anton for detail.

9.2 Linear differentiation equations of order greater than one

Adapted from Text book by Tenenbaun and Pollard (1964) (P196-231).

Definition 18.1 Linear differential equation of order n is

$$18.11 \quad f_n(x)y^{(n)} + f_{n-1}(x)y^{(n-1)} + \dots + f_1(x)y' + f_0(x)y = Q(x)$$

where $f_0(x), f_1(x), \dots, f_n(x)$ and $Q(x)$ are each continuous functions of x defined on a common interval I and $f_n(x) \neq 0$ in I (means $f_n(x)$ is not equal to zero for every x in I). Note, *linear* means the $y^{(n)}, y^{(n-1)}, \dots, y'$ terms are in linear, e.g., not in, say, $[y^{(n)}]^2, \dots$

- If $Q(x) \neq 0$ in I , (18.11) is called a *non-homogeneous equation*.
- If $Q(x) \equiv 0$ in I , (18.11) is called a *homogeneous equation*.

Lesson 18: complex numbers and complex functions

$z = a + bi$, is a complex number in which a, b are real numbers (rational or irrational), i is defined as $i^2 = -1$. a is the real part of z and b is the imaginary part of z .

Theorem 18.23: Fundamental theorem of algebra

Every equation of the form

$$a_n(x)^n + a_{n-1}x^{n-1} + \dots + a_1x + a_0 = 0, \quad a_n \neq 0$$

where the a 's are complex numbers, has at least one root but not more than n distinct roots. It's left side can be written as

$$a_n(x)(x - r_1)(x - r_2)\dots(x - r_n)$$

where the r 's are complex numbers which need not be distinct.

Definition 18.3 If $z = a + bi$, the conjugate of z is $\bar{z} = a - bi$.

Definition 18.31 If $z = a + bi$, the absolute value of z is $|z| = \sqrt{b^2 + a^2}$.

$$(18.4) \quad |z| = r = \sqrt{x^2 + y^2}$$

$$(18.41) \quad x = r \cos \theta$$

$$(18.42) \quad y = r \sin \theta$$

$$(18.52) \quad z = r \cos \theta + ir \sin \theta = r(\cos \theta + i \sin \theta)$$

(18.54) The polar angle θ in Figure (3) is called *argument* of z , written as $Argz$. $\cos \theta = \frac{x}{|z|}$, $\sin \theta = \frac{y}{|z|}$. $Argz$ is the principal value of θ , for other values, $argz = Argz \pm 2n\pi$.

Lesson 18B Algebra of complex numbers of, $z_1 = a + bi$ and $z_2 = c + di$

$$18.6 \quad z_1 + z_2 = (a + bi) + (c + di) = (a + c) + (b + d)i$$

$$z_1 - z_2 = (a + bi) - (c + di) = (a - c) + (b - d)i$$

$$z_1 z_2 = (a + bi)(c + di) = ac + adi + bci + bdi^2 = (ac + bd) + (ad + bc)i$$

$$z_1/z_2 = \frac{a + bi}{c + di} \cdot \frac{c - di}{c - di} = \frac{ac + bd}{c^2 + d^2} + \frac{bc - ad}{c^2 + d^2}i, \quad c^2 + d^2 \neq 0$$

Figure 3: *Relation between rectangular and polar coordinates*

Lesson 18C Exponential, Trig, Hyperbolic functions of complex numbers

According to Maclaurin series, for real number x ,

$$18.7 \quad e^x = 1 + \frac{x}{1!} + \frac{x^2}{2!} + \frac{x^3}{3!} + \dots, \quad -\infty < x < \infty$$

$$18.71 \quad \sin x = x - \frac{x^3}{3!} + \frac{x^5}{5!} - \dots, \quad -\infty < x < \infty$$

$$18.72 \quad \cos x = 1 - \frac{x^2}{2!} + \frac{x^4}{4!} - \dots, \quad -\infty < x < \infty$$

These formulas also hold true for complex numbers. Each of the series converges for all z .

$$18.73 \quad e^z = 1 + \frac{z}{1!} + \frac{z^2}{2!} + \frac{z^3}{3!} + \dots$$

$$18.74 \quad \sin z = z - \frac{z^3}{3!} + \frac{z^5}{5!} - \dots,$$

$$18.75 \quad \cos z = 1 - \frac{z^2}{2!} + \frac{z^4}{4!} - \dots,$$

For example, $\cos i = 1 + \frac{1}{2!} + \frac{1}{4!} + \dots$, (a real number).

The following are useful identities for complex numbers:

$$18.8 \quad e^0 = 1$$

$$18.81 \quad e_1^z e_2^z = e^{z_1+z_2}$$

$$18.82 \quad e^{iz} = \cos z + i \sin z$$

$$18.83 \quad e^{-iz} = \cos z - i \sin z$$

$$18.84 \quad \sin z = \frac{1}{2i}(e^{iz} - e^{-iz})$$

$$18.85 \quad \cos z = \frac{1}{2}(e^{iz} + e^{-iz})$$

$$18.86 \quad e^z \neq 0 \quad \text{for any value of } z$$

The combination $\frac{e^z - e^{-z}}{2}$ and $\frac{e^z + e^{-z}}{2}$ appear frequently, they are given special symbols:

$$18.9 \quad \sinh z = \frac{e^z - e^{-z}}{2} \quad \text{Hyperbolic Sine}$$

$$18.91 \quad \cosh z = \frac{e^z + e^{-z}}{2} \quad \text{Hyperbolic Cosine}$$

$$18.92 \quad \tanh z = \frac{\sinh z}{\cosh z} = \frac{e^z - e^{-z}}{e^z + e^{-z}} \quad \text{Hyperbolic Tangent}$$

Lesson 19 Linear independence of functions. The linear DE of order n .

Lesson 19A Linear independence of functions.

Definition 19.1 A set of functions $f_1(x), f_2(x), \dots, f_n(x)$, each defined on a common interval I , is called linearly dependent on I , if there exists a set of constants c_1, c_2, \dots, c_n , not all zero, such that

$$19.11 \quad c_1 f_1(x) + c_2 f_2(x) + \dots + c_n f_n(x) = 0$$

for every x in I . If no such set of constants, c_1, c_2, \dots, c_n , exists, then the set of functions is called linearly independent.

Definition 19.12 The left-hand side of (19.11) is called linear combination of the set functions $f_1(x), f_2(x), \dots, f_n(x)$.

Examples:

$$1. \quad x, -2x, -3x, 4x, \quad I: -\infty < x < \infty \quad (\text{linearly dependent})$$

$$2. \quad x^p, x^q \quad I: x > 0, x < 0. \quad (\text{linearly independent})$$

$$3. \quad e^{px}, e^{qx} \quad I: p \neq q \quad -\infty < x < \infty \quad (\text{Linearly independent})$$

4. $e^x, 0, \sin x, 1, \quad I: -\infty < x < \infty$ (linearly dependent)

Comment 19.14 Whenever a set of functions contains zero for one of its members, the set must be linearly dependent. All you have to do is to choose every C the value zero, except the one which is the coefficient of zero.

Lesson 19B The linear differential equation of order n

Theorem 19.2 If $f_0(x), f_1(x), \dots, f_n(x)$ and $Q(x)$ are each continuous functions of x on a common interval I , and $f_n(x) \neq 0$ when x is in I , then the linear differential equation

$$f_n(x)y^{(n)} + f_{n-1}(x)y^{(n-1)} + \dots + f_1(x)y' + f_0(x)y = Q(x)$$

has one and only one solution,

$$19.22 \quad y = y(x)$$

satisfying the set of initial conditions

$$19.23 \quad y(x_0) = y_0, y'(x_0) = y_1, \dots, y^{(n-1)}(x_0) = y_{n-1},$$

where x_0 is in I , and y_0, y_1, \dots, y_{n-1} are constants.

Theorem 19.3 If $f_0(x), f_1(x), \dots, f_n(x)$ and $Q(x)$ are each continuous functions of x on a common interval I , and $f_n(x) \neq 0$ when x is in I , then:

1. The homogeneous d.e.

$$19.31 \quad f_n(x)y^{(n)} + f_{n-1}(x)y^{(n-1)} + \dots + f_1(x)y' + f_0(x)y = 0$$

has n linearly independent solutions, $y_1(x), y_2(x), \dots, y_n(x)$.

2. The linear combination of the n solutions

$$19.32 \quad y_c(x) = c_1y_1(x) + c_2y_2(x) + \dots + c_ny_n(x),$$

where c_1, c_2, \dots, c_n are a set of n arbitrary constants, is also a solution of (19.31). It's an n -parameter family of solutions of (19.31).

3. The function

$$19.33 \quad y(x) = y_c(x) + y_p(x),$$

where $y_c(x)$ is defined in (19.32) and $y_p(x)$ is a particular solution of the non-homogeneous linear d.e. corresponding to (19.31), namely,

$$19.34 \quad f_n(x)y^{(n)} + f_{n-1}(x)y^{(n-1)} + \dots + f_1(x)y' + f_0(x)y = Q(x)$$

is an n -parameter family solutions of (19.34).

In the proof of 2 of theorem 19.3, an important relationship wa used:

$$u''(x) + v''(x) = \frac{d^2u(x)}{dx^2} + \frac{d^2v(x)}{dx^2} = \frac{d^2(u + v)}{dx^2} = (u + v)''$$

For higher order derivatives, this applies too!

$$c_1y_1^{(n)} + c_2y_2^{(n)} + \dots + c_ny_n^{(n)} = [c_1y_1 + c_1y_2 + \dots + c_ny_n]^{(n)}$$

Definition 19.4 The general solution $y_c(x)$ in (19.32) of the homogeneous equation (19.31) is called *the complimentary function* of (19.34).

Lesson 20 Solution of the homogeneous linear d.e. of order n with constant coefficients

Lesson 20A General form of its solution.

To get solution for

$$20.1 \quad a_ny^{(n)} + a_{n-1}y^{(n-1)} + \dots + a_1y' + a_0y = 0$$

where a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n are constants and $a_n \neq 0$, we first write the characteristic equation for (20.1)

$$20.14 \quad a_nm^n + a_{n-1}m^{n-1} + \dots + a_1m + a_0 = 0$$

According to theorem (18.23), (20.14) has at least one solution, but no more than n distinct solutions. Let us call these n roots (solutions) m_1, m_2, \dots, m_n , where the m 's need not all be distinct. Then each function

$$20.15 \quad y_1 = e^{m_1x}, \quad y_2 = e^{m_2x}, \quad \dots, \quad y_n = e^{m_nx}$$

is a solution of (20.1).

There are three possibilities for detailed solutions to (20.1):

- Lesson 20B. *Roots of the characteristic equation (20.14) real and distinct.*

If the n roots m_1, m_2, \dots, m_n , of the characteristic equation (20.14) are distinct, then the n solutions of (20.1), namely,

$$20.2 \quad y_1 = e^{m_1x}, \quad y_2 = e^{m_2x}, \quad \dots, \quad y_n = e^{m_nx}$$

are linearly independent functions. Hence by theorem (19.3),

$$20.21y_c = c_1e^{m_1x} + c_2e^{m_2x} + \dots + c_ne^{m_nx}$$

is the general solution of (20.1).

- Lesson 20C. *Roots of the characteristic equation (20.14) real but some multiple.*
If two or more roots of the characteristic equation (20.14) are alike, then the functions (20.156) formed with each of these n roots are not linearly independent. In general, it can be shown that if characteristic equation (20.14) has a root $m = a$, which repeats n times, then the general solution of (20.1) is,

$$20.4 \quad y_c = (c_1 + c_2x + c_3x^2 + \dots + c_nx^{n-1})e^{ax}$$

And if, for example, the characteristic equation (20.14) can be written in the form

$$20.41 \quad m^2(m - a)^3(m + b)^4(m + c) = 0$$

which implies that its roots are $m = 0$ twice, $m = a$ three times, $m = -b$ four times, $m = -c$ once. Then the general solution of its related d.e. is

$$y_c = c_1 + c_2x + (c_3 + c_4x + c_5x^2)e^{ax} + (c_6 + c_7x + c_8x^2 + c_9x^3)e^{-bx} + c_{10}e^{-cx}$$

Observe that with each m -fold root p , e^{px} is multiplied by a linear combination of powers of x beginning with x^0 and ending with x^{n-1}

- Lesson 20D. *Roots of the characteristic equation (20.14) imaginary.*

If the constant coefficients in the characteristic equation (20.14) are real, then any imaginary roots it may have must occur in conjugate pairs. Hence if $\alpha + \beta i$ is one root, another root must be $\alpha - \beta i$.

For a d.e. of order two, whose characteristic equation has the conjugate roots $\alpha + \beta i$ and $\alpha - \beta i$, the general solution can be written in any of the following forms:

$$\begin{aligned} 20.6 \quad y_c &= c_1e^{(\alpha+\beta i)x} + c_2e^{\alpha-\beta i} \\ y_c &= e^{\alpha x}(c_1 \cos \beta x + c_2 \sin \beta x) \\ y_c &= ce^{\alpha x} \sin(\beta x - \delta) \\ y_c &= ce^{\alpha x} \cos(\beta x + \delta) \end{aligned}$$

For example, if the o.d.e.

$$20.7 \quad a_4y(4) + a_3y''' + a_2y'' + a_1y' + a_0 = 0, a_4 \neq 0$$

has a conjugate pair of repeated imaginary roots, i.e., if $\alpha + \beta i$ and $\alpha - \beta i$ each occurs twice as a root, then the general solution of (20.7) is

$$20.71 \quad y_c = (c_1 + c_2x)e^{(\alpha+i\beta)x} + (c_3 + c_4x)e^{(\alpha-i\beta)x}$$

The equivalent forms are

$$\begin{aligned}y_c &= e^{\alpha x}[(c_1 + c_2 x) \cos \beta x + (c_3 + c_4 x) \sin \beta x] \\y_c &= e^{\alpha x}[c_1 \sin(\beta x + \delta_1) + c_2 \sin(\beta x + \delta_2)] \\y_c &= e^{\alpha x}[c_1 \cos(\beta x - \delta_1) + c_2 \cos(\beta x - \delta_2)]\end{aligned}$$

Lesson 21 Solution of the non-homogeneous linear differential equations of order n with constant coefficients

Lesson 21A Solution by the method of undetermined coefficients.

By theorem 19.3 and comment 19.41, the general solution of the differential equation

$$20.1 \quad a_n y^{(n)} + a_{n-1} y^{(n-1)} + \dots + a_1 y' + a_0 y = Q(x)$$

where $a_n \neq 0$, and $Q(x) \neq 0$ in an interval I , is

$$20.11 \quad y(x) = y_c(x) + y_p(x),$$

where $y_c(x)$, the complimentary function, is the general solution of the related homogeneous equation (21.1) and $y_p(x)$ is a particular solution of (21.1). In lesson 20, we showed how to find y_c , now we show how to find y_p .

- Case 1. No term of $Q(x)$ in (21.1) is the same as a term in y_c . In this case, a particular solution of (21.1) will be a linear combination of the term in $Q(x)$ and *all* its linearly independent derivatives.
- Case 2. $Q(x)$ in (21.1) contains a term which, ignoring constant coefficients, is x^k times a term $u(x)$ of y_c , where k is zero or a positive integer. In this case, a particular solution, y_p of (21.1) will be linear combination of $x^{k+1}u(x)$ and all its linearly independent derivatives (ignoring constant terms). If in addition $Q(x)$ contains terms which belongs to Case 1, then the proper terms called for by this case must be included in y_p .
- Case 3. This is the case applicable only if both of the following conditions are fulfilled:
 1. The characteristic equation of the given d.e. (21.1) has an r multiple root.
 2. $Q(x)$ contains a terms which, ignoring constant coefficients, is x^k times a term $u(x)$ in y_c , where $u(x)$ was obtained from the r multiple root.

Lesson 21B. Solution by the use of complex variables.

If in

$$21.5 \quad a_n y^{(n)} + a_{n-1} y^{(n-1)} + \dots + a_1 y' + a_0 y = Q(x), a_n \neq 0$$

the a 's are real, $Q(x)$ is a complex-valued function and $y_p(x)$ is a solution to (21.5), then:

1. The real part of y_p is a solution of (21.5) with $Q(x)$ replaced by its real part.
2. The remaining part of y_p is a solution of (21.5) with $Q(x)$ replaced by its imaginary part.

10 Differences between function and subroutine in structured programs

Structured programming plays an important role in scientific data analysis. Function and subroutine are two important structures to break down a computer program into smaller, functional units for efficient testing and debugging. Here I use a True Basic program to show some of the main differences of external functions and external subroutines (internal functions and subroutines can also be used but external versions are more useful as variables inside those structures are **localized** from the calling program unit).

```
PROGRAM func_sub
! Author: Xuejun Dong
! Date: November 27, 2017

! This program demonstrates the differences between
! external function and subroutines as used in
! True Basic.

DECLARE DEF Func
let a = 3
let b = 4
let hypoten = 0

PRINT "Initial values of a, b, and hypoten are:"
PRINT "a=";a, "b=";b, "hypoten=";hypoten
PRINT

PRINT "Press any key to call functon Func..."
GET KEY k ! Hold output until a key is pressed
PRINT

let hypoten = Func(a,b)
PRINT "but not in the main program."
PRINT
PRINT "This can be verified by printing a, b and hypoten from within the main program:"
PRINT
PRINT "Press any key to verify this..."
GET KEY k ! Hold output until a key is pressed
PRINT
PRINT "a=";a, "b=";b, "hypoten=";hypoten
PRINT
PRINT "It is clear that after Func was called,"
PRINT "only the value of hypoten was updated, but not that of a or b!"
PRINT
PRINT
```

```

PRINT "Now press any key to test subroutine Funct()..."
GET KEY k ! Hold output until a key is pressed
PRINT

call Funct (a,b,hypoten)
PRINT "We can see that these modifications have also affected"
PRINT "the values of a and b in the main program,"
PRINT "along the hypoten:"
PRINT
PRINT "a=";a, "b=";b, "hypoten=";hypoten
PRINT

PRINT "For this reason, in the subroutine Funct,"
PRINT "parameter x (corresponding to argument a) is called input parameter,"
PRINT "as it only provides information for "
PRINT "determining the values of some other parameters,"
PRINT "but its value is not changed after the subroutine is called."
PRINT "Parameter y (corresponding to argument b) is called an input/output parameter,"
PRINT "as it provides information for determining other parameters "
PRINT "while its value also changed after the subroutine is called."
PRINT "Parameter z (corresponding to argument hypoten) is called output parameter,"
PRINT "because its value is determined based on values of input parameters."

PRINT
PRINT "Press any key to close the program!"
GET KEY k ! Hold output until a key is pressed
PRINT
END

DEF Func (a,b)
  let hypot = sqr(a^2 + b^2)
  let a=a*10
  let b=b*10
  PRINT "Values of a and b are modified only within Func:"
  PRINT "a=";a, "b=";b
  PRINT
  let Func = hypot
END DEF

SUB Funct (x,y,z)
  PRINT "Immediately after arguments a and b are passed to the subroutine Funct,"
  PRINT "the values of parameters x and y are:"
  PRINT "x=";x, "y=";y
  PRINT

```

```

let z = sqr(x^2 + y^2)
let y=y*100
PRINT "At the end of the subroutine, the values of x and y are modified as"
PRINT "x=";x, "y=";y
PRINT
END SUB

```

We use an external function `Func` (which must be declared at the beginning of the calling program using statement `DECLARE DEF`) to calculate the length of hypotenuse of a right triangle based on values of the two sides forming the right angle (`a`, and `b`).

The advantage of using an external function (as opposed to using a subroutine) is that only one value is returned but the arguments (`a,b`) are not changed, because when the function is called only the value of the argument is passed to the function (to replace the parameter (although they have the same names `a`, and `b`, but actually they are variables different from `a` and `b` as used in the main program unit)). This is called *passing by value*.

Essentially, during implementation, the values of the arguments are copied to temporarily assign values to `a` and `b` inside the function structure, so that the value of the hypotenuse is calculated and returned to the calling program unit. However, the original values of `a`, `b` in the main program will not be modified.

On the other hand, if a subroutine is used here in place of the function, the values of the arguments may be modified. Instead of passing by value, in the implementation of a subroutine, values of arguments are *passed by reference* but not being copied to the subroutine. Essentially, during implementation, the argument variables (`a,b, hypoten`) are associated with the corresponding parameter variables of the subroutine (`x,y,z`), so that the subroutine (when called) knows what values to use in order to correctly conduct the required calculations as specified in the subroutine. This way, no values are actually copied from the calling program unit to the sub-program unit. Thus, it saves memory if some of the arguments are arrays (which take considerable memory if copied from one place to another, especially when the arrays are big).

11 How to run a Fortran program on a Windows computer

11.1 Basics

Assume first that the GFortran compiler is installed. For example, on X. Dong's new computer, LAPTOP HP ELITEBOOK 830 G5, it is installed at C:\Program Files (x86)\mingw-w64\i686-8.1.0-posix-dwarf-rt_v6-rev0. Using several double clicks on Windows to see the contents of the above directory. Then double click on the Windows batch file mingw-w64 to launch a DOS-like command-line window. Within this command-line window, using standard DOS commands to move the computer cursor under the folder in which your Fortran program is stored on this computer. For X. Dong's new computer, Fortran programs are collected under C:\Users\Xuejun.Dong\Desktop\Computing\g95\xd_f_programs. Suppose we are going to run a program called `fact.for`, which is to calculate the factorial of 5 ²³.

```
      program FACT
! Roman Groger's Tutorial.
! Standard Fortran uses "c" or "*" to start a comment line,
! but using the exclamation "!" is also acceptable mostly.
! Definition of variables
      integer i, res, number
      parameter( number = 5 )
      res = 1
      do i=2,number ! this loop calculates the factorial
         res = res*i
      enddo
      write(*,('Factorial of ',I3,' is ',I5))
+ number, res
      end
```

Now enter this command `gfortran fact.for -o fact.exe`, and followed by ENTER. This will prompt GFortran to compile the original program and create an executable file called `fact.exe`. No more information will be displayed if no syntax error is found in the program `fact.for`. Or, if there are syntax errors, you will have to go back to your text editor to correct the errors, and compile the program again to get the executable file. To run this program to get expected result, you just enter `fact`, and followed by ENTER. There, you should see the correct result is printed on the DOS screen.

²³Fortran does not distinguish between upper and lower case letters. Also note that Fortran 77 uses standard fixed format, in which executable commands must be put from columns 7 through 73, and the first column is reserved for comment symbol, such as "c", "*", or "!". Columns 2-5 are reserved for integer numbers labeling specific lines of code. If a line is too long, it can be broken and continued in next line starting at column 6 with special symbol (here in this program a "+" is used).

11.2 Compiling subroutines together with the main program, or separately

When a programmer's task becomes more complex, it is often desirable to break down the main task into small units. In fortran they are called program units, which can be functions or subroutines. In F90 or later, it may also include Modules, collections of a number of functions or subroutines. Here is a tutorial showing different ways to compile a Fortran which calls a number of subroutines. the test programs are adapted from the following website (with modifications):

<https://www.physicsforums.com/threads/fortran-77-subroutine-in-separate-file.473952/>

Suppose we have one subroutine called SUB.FOR that is to be called by two main programs, test1.for and test2.for.

```

SUBROUTINE SUB(A, B, C, TOT)
c Source https://www.physicsforums.com/threads/
c fortran-77-subroutine-in-separate-file.473952/
  INTEGER TOT, A, B, C, I
  TOT = C
  DO 10 I = A,B
    TOT = TOT*I
10  END DO
  RETURN
END

PROGRAM TEST1
c Source https://www.physicsforums.com/threads/
c fortran-77-subroutine-in-separate-file.473952/
  IMPLICIT NONE
  INTEGER X, Y, Z, TOTAL, TOT
  PRINT *, 'Enter numbers X,Y,Z where Y > X'
  READ *, X, Y, Z
  CALL SUB(X, Y, Z, TOTAL)
  PRINT *, 'TOTAL =', TOTAL
END

PROGRAM TEST2
c Source https://www.physicsforums.com/threads/
c fortran-77-subroutine-in-separate-file.473952/
  IMPLICIT NONE
  INTEGER X, Y, Z, TOTAL, TOT
  PRINT *, 'Enter numbers X,Y,Z where Y > X'
  READ *, X, Y, Z
  CALL SUB(X, Y, Z, TOTAL)
  TOTAL = TOTAL + TOTAL
  PRINT *, 'TWICE TOTAL =', TOTAL
END
```

11.2.1 Compiling with the main program

Realizing that the subroutine is called by the main program, we can modify the main program by appending the external subroutine directly at the end of the main program and save the program file as `test1a.for`:

```
PROGRAM TEST1a
c Source https://www.physicsforums.com/threads/fortran-77-subroutine-in-separate-file.473952/
IMPLICIT NONE
INTEGER X, Y, Z, TOTAL, TOT
PRINT *, 'Enter numbers X,Y,Z where Y > X'
READ *, X, Y, Z
CALL SUB(X, Y, Z, TOTAL)
PRINT *, 'TOTAL =', TOTAL
END

SUBROUTINE SUB(A, B, C, TOT)
c Source https://www.physicsforums.com/threads/fortran-77-subroutine-in-separate-file.473952/
INTEGER TOT, A, B, C, I
TOT = C
DO 10 I = A,B
TOT = TOT*I
10 END DO
RETURN
END
```

Now we can compile the main program as usual:
`gfortran test1a.for -o test1a.exe`

11.2.2 Compiling separately and then linked to the main program

In order to save time for compiling the same subroutine repeatedly, we can compile it separately using `gfortran sub.for -c`. This will generate an object file called `SUB.O`. Now, we can link this object file with two main programs that both call this subroutine:

```
gfortran test1.for sub.o -o test1.exe
gfortran test2.for sub.o -o test2.exe.
```

The same can be done if we have more than one subroutines, all called by the main programs. Alternatively, we can use a mixture of the above approaches: that is, some subroutines can be compiled together with the main program, while others be compiled separately as shown above. These sample programs are saved under the folder `xd_f_programs` on X. Dong's new computer.

11.3 Using gfortran under Cygwin

One of the computers in my lab is installed with `gfortran` under `Cygwin`. Since `Cygwin` mimics `Unix` commands on a Windows computer, the way to navigate from folder to folder (in `Cygwin`, it is Directory) and to get access to files is different from using a DOS command line window. Here are a few things that I observed:

- Double clicking the `Cygwin Terminal` icon will bring us to the current user directory. On my lab computer in particular, it is `Xuejun.Dong@UVC-206HM-L~`. From there, we can navigate to the upper and down stream folders ²⁴.
- Different from the DOS system, in `Cygwin`, levels of directories are specified using a forward slash (e.g., `/`) instead of a backslash. Also different from DOS, `Cygwin` is case sensitive.
- Under `Cygwin`, to run a compiled Fortran program, we use `./a.exe`. However, when using `gfortran` under `mingw-w64`, we just enter `a.exe` followed by a RETURN.
- I noticed that the executables generated by `gfortran` under `Cygwin` have smaller file size (can be 50% smaller) than those generated in `gfortran` installed with `mingw-w64`.

Finally, on my lab computer, all `fortran` programs are gathered under this folder:
`C:\cygwin64\home\Xuejun.Dong\g95\xd_f_programs`.

11.4 Using g77 under Cygwin

In 2009 when I was at NDSU, I used `g77` under `Cygwin` in order to run Fortran programs from Dr. Bernd A. Berg's book, *Markov Chain Monte Carlo Simulations And Their Statistical Analysis: With Web-based Fortran Code*.

The following are the tips that I used in getting myself started with `g77` with `Cygwin`:

- First I downloaded `Cygwin` from <http://www.cygwin.com/>. Dr. Berg suggested to install a full version, so that later I can be able to use `g77` within this system. A good explanation of how to install of full version of `Cygwin` can be found at <http://www.physionet.org/physiotools/cygwin/>²⁵.
- Then, I downloaded the computer file `STMC.tgz` from Dr. Berg's home page (<http://www.hep.fsu.edu/~berg/>). It is interesting that the file name extension automatically changed into `.tar` after downloading. However, I still changed the extension to `.tgz`, so that I could unfold the file tree of the programs. Within `Cygwin`, there is a `home` folder in which a folder `Xuejun Dong` was generated automatically. This is the user name of my computer. I at first put the file `STMC.tgz` under this folder and hit `tar -zxvf STMC.tgz` to unfold the tree structure. And it did! However, I had a worry

²⁴See a good reference of the pdf document `Cygwin_tutorial_slides.pdf`.

²⁵When I selected packages, I clicked on the rotating selector next to "All" (at the top of the Category list) so that the indicator to its right changed from "Default" to "Install".

that the Linux system does not allow spaces between directory names. So, I moved the whole folder of STMC into another folder, which I generated following a suggestion at this website: <http://www.physionet.org/physiotools/cygwin/>. Specifically, the following commands were run under the Cygwin terminal window:

```
mkdir /home/xdong
echo "export HOME=/home/xdong" >>.bashrc
echo "export HOME=/home/xdong" >>.bash_profile
cp .bashrc .bash_profile /home/xdong
echo "cd" >>.bashrc
```

- Dr. Berg has built a very structured file system, in which some of the subroutines and dataset are used repeatedly by many programs. This tree system allows a very efficient use of the low-level FORTRAN programs. In particular, he stored all the exercises in the Assignments folder, which is under the STMC folder. Because the computer programs are located within some other folders (located also within the STMC folder), he used an interesting way to cross-reference the subroutines located in different folders. For example, assignment program `mar.f` is located in `...\STMC\Assignments\a0102_02` folder. However, this program needs to use a subroutine `rmaset.f`, which is located in `...\STMC\ForLib\` folder. So, a line, `include '../..../ForLib/rmaset.f'`, is added at the end of program `mar.f`. Here, `../` means to *go to one layer up to the outer level of the folder*. Because the program `mar.f` is located in folder `...\STMC\Assignments\a0102_02`, so moving twice toward the outer layer will bring us to folder STMC. As such `../..../ForLib/rmaset.f` is equivalent to `../STMC/ForLib/rmaset.f`, in which `...` just is the abbreviation of additional layers. Here it stands for `C:\cygwin\home\xdong`. In this way, Dr. Berg can refer to any subroutines that are located in this tree structure.
- The `g77` can be run anywhere within the folder system by `g77 -O filename.f`²⁶. Here “-O” is the minus sign (“-”) and capital letter “O”, instead of zero or lower-case letter “o”. This will generate a file `a.exe` within this current folder (where `filename.f` is located). Next, we can run this `exe` file by entering `./a.exe`. So, it is very convenient to run any program from within the folder system of STMC tree.
- To go to a folder one layer up of our current folder, we simply use `cd ../` in the Cygwin terminal. To go the the next lower level folder, we simply use `cd foldername`. Entering `cd` alone will bring back to the home folder. The command `exit` can be used to close the Cygwin terminal.
- To view a folder’s content, we use `ls`.
- Other useful commands can be found on the internet by searching Linux tutorial.

²⁶We first need to go to the current folder storing our interested program.

12 Matlab for scientific computing

12.1 Basics

The main reasons for me to use Matlab are (1) it has a collection of large number of toolboxes to implement numerical computing algorithms, and (2) it has a simple, pseudo code-like syntax²⁷ to implement numerical algorithms. In general, as a interpreted language, Matlab is a bit slower at run time than C/Fortran, but this would not be a concern for moderate and small sized computing work, as it usually is for problems in agriculture and biology. The main reward is that, Matlab can liberate biologists from tedious, and error-prone, process of writing and debugging lower-level codes, and thus would increase work efficiency in the long-run. The only disadvantage that I can think of is that Matlab is a commercial software, especially if one heavily relies on the numerous toolboxes in addition to the core package.

Matlab has a rich set of data types (15 or more). However, unlike some lower-level languages, Matlab does not require a variable to be declared explicitly before being used. For example, in the Matlab Command line, if we create a variable `x = 6`, Matlab treats it not as an integer, but a double-precision, floating point number.

After launching the Matlab user interface, we can see three windows displayed: the Command window, the Workspace window and the Current Folder window.

- Command window is where the user interacts with Matlab by entering commands and seeing the results. The displayed items on the Command window can be cleared using `clc`. This, however, will not affect the Command history, which can be accessed by issuing the command `commandhistory` in the Command window²⁸. The user can copy-paste the contents in the Command history to the Script window to compose a Matlab script or function by right-clicking on portion of selected text in the history window and select **New Script**.
- Workspace window stores all the variables generated in the Matlab global environment²⁹. Variables in the Workspace window can be saved for reuse later. Or, if they are not saved before closing the Matlab user interface window, they will be lost. Issuing the command `save` will save all workspace variables to the machine readable file `matlab.mat` at the current directory. Command `clear`³⁰ will clear all variables, and `load` will reload all the variables previously saved to `matlab.mat`.
- Current Folder window displays all the saved data objects, especially Matlab scripts and functions (`.m` files) that are generated in current Matlab session, or was generated in the past³¹. Functions/scripts stored at Current Folder, as well as other folders

²⁷Here is a very good discussion comparing Matlab with some lower-level languages, such as C and Fortran: <https://www.mathworks.com/matlabcentral/answers/358105-is-matlab-a-compiler>

²⁸This is similar to Minitab's History window

²⁹This is relative to the local environment reserved for storing variables for different functions; these local variables cannot be directly accessed from within the global environment, as well as from other functions.

³⁰Different from this, command `clf` will clear current graph.

³¹Assuming this folder is set as the default user path.

residing in Matlab's search path, can be accessed from the Command line window, as well as from within a main function³². This is an important point and will be discussed further in next section.

12.2 Scripts and functions

Matlab scripts are collections of Matlab commands that are saved as `.m` files³³ and can be run by typing the names of the scripts at Command line. Functions, both builtin functions and user-defined ones, can be called within the body of scripts.

Different from some low-level programming languages, in Matlab, subroutines and functions are combined as functions. The main activities in Matlab programs are function calls. As a result, functions is the heart of Matlab programming.

- *Main functions.* The first listed function in a function `.m` file is called the main function. As a convention, the name of the function file must be the same as the name of the main function.
- *Local functions.* Local functions are functions created in the same function file, but listed after the main function. Typically, local functions are called by the main function or by other local functions residing in the same file after the main function. However, ordinarily, local functions residing in one function file are not visible to other functions (i.e., not listed in the same file). In case of having multiple local functions listed in the same function file, the order of list is not important.
- *Nested function.* These are functions fully residing within other functions. Nested functions can access to variables in the functions that “house” them³⁴.
- *Builtin functions.* These are functions built-in in Matlab. For example, `sin()`, `cos()` `length()` are all built-in functions; these can be called by a user-defined function.
- *Function handles - definition.* Function handle - used with an `@` operator and as a data type in Matlab - can be frequently used to pass functions to other functions. For example, we can create a handle to the `sin` function by issuing the following command:

```
f = @sin;
```

Then, we can use the builtin function `fminbnd` to find the value of x that minimizes `sin(x)` in the range from 0 to $\frac{4\pi}{3}$:

³²This is relative to local functions residing in a function file but are listed *after* the main function.

³³The names of script files cannot be the same as names of the function files that are included in the scripts; and functions in the scripts must be placed at the end of the script files.

³⁴This is in contrast to the general rule that all variables within a function, regardless of type, are local and the only way for functions to communicate with one another is by passing arguments.

```
minv = fminbnd(f,0,pi*4/3);
fprintf('The sin function has a minimum when x = %4.2f\n',minv)
```

The result displayed on the screen is:

```
The sin function has a minimum when x = 4.19
```

Next let's show two ways of passing a function handle to another function. Given a quadratic equation

$$y = x^2 + 2x + 3,$$

the integral from 0 to 1 is

$$y_{int} = \int_0^1 (x^2 + 2x + 3) dx = 4\frac{1}{3}.$$

Now let's use Matlab to find this definite integral. As a first way, let's create a function called `qdrate.m` and save it under current folder.

```
% A function for testing function handle...
function y = qdrate(x)
y = x.^2 + 2*x + 3;
end
```

Now enter the following command in the Command line:

```
q = integral(@qdrate,0,1)
```

We get the following result:

```
q =
    4.3333
```

Alternately, we can create a handle to a one-line *anonymous function*, pass it to the builtin function `integral` and see if we can get the same result as above.

```
f = @(x) x.^2 + 2*x + 3;
q1 = integral(f,0,1)
```

And we did get the same result:

```
q1 =  
    4.3333
```

- *Function handles - its use to get access to local functions from the Command line.* In Matlab, local functions appended to the main function in a .m file normally are not visible at the Command line or to other functions residing in the current folder. However, they can become visible if we create function handles to local functions using the function of `localfunctions`, as shown in the following example adapted from Matlab Documentation. First let's create a function `EllipseVals.m`:

```
% Adapted from Matlab Documentation  
function fh = EllipseVals    % Main function visible by other functions  
    fh = localfunctions;  
end  
  
function f = Focus(a,b)    % local function 1 in this file  
    f = sqrt(a^2-b^2);  
end  
  
function e = Eccentricity(a,b)    % local function 2 in this file  
    f = Focus(a,b);  
    e = f/a;  
end  
  
function ae = Area(a,b)    % local function 3 in this file  
    ae = pi*a*b;  
end
```

Then find out the handle from the Command line:

```
fh = EllipseVals
```

We will see the following display:

```
fh =  
  
    3x1 cell array
```

```
{      @Focus}
{@Eccentricity}
{      @Area}
```

Note that the `Area` function handle is the 3rd element in the cell array. Enter this command `fh{3}(3,1)` will call the local function `Area (a,b)` with argument `(3,1)`. As expected, the answer is:

```
ans =
     9.4248
```

The very reason why a function handle, once defined for a local function, can be accessed by other functions, is that the function handle preserves the absolute path of the function with which it is associated.

- *Finding out descriptions of functions.* Over time, with the accumulation of custom functions under current folder, the user him/herself would not remember the nature of the functions he/she created before. To get an overview of a function, use `which` function. This only applies to main functions. If the name of the local function is known, the operator `>` can be used to find out its description. For example, I have a function `EllipseVals.m` saved in current folder, and inside this function there is a local function called `Focus(a,b)`. From Command line, I can use the following command to get an overview of `Focus`:

```
which EllipseVals>Focus
```

The result is:

```
C:\Users\Xuejun.Dong\Documents\MATLAB\xd_matlearn\EllipseVals.m
(Focus)  % Local function of EllipseVals
```

- *Comments and documentation* To comment out a line of code, use a `%` sign. However, if you type `%%`, Matlab will consider it a “cell” driver for publishing (see Sub-section 12.6). This has nothing to do with the data type “cell array”, but defines the start of cell publishing - a mechanism to intermingle code, command window outputs including graphics, in a \LaTeX (or html/Word) file. In addition to using a single `%` to comment out one line at a time, one can use the pair `%{` and `%{` to comment out a block of lines.
- *MEX file functions.* A MEX file is a function created in Matlab that can call C/C++ programs or Fortran subroutines from Matlab Command line.

12.3 Matlab data types

There are many data types in Matlab. Since variables are not explicitly declared when used in a function, it can take considerable amount of time for a new user to understand common data types and their proper uses in Matlab. A user can only gradually increase his/her vocabulary of Matlab data types through practice. Here are a few items to consider:

- *Character arrays vs. string arrays.* I think a post by Steven Lord at the following website illustrates well the difference between a character array and a string array from a user's perspective.

```
https://www.mathworks.com/matlabcentral/answers/361783-what-are-the-internal-differences-between-matlab-strings-and-character-arrays
```

“A string array treats each phrase as a unit, whereas a char array treats each character as a unit.” That means a character array is a matrix of individual characters. Steven Load gives the following example³⁵ by creating a character array at Command line:

```
c = ['apple '; 'banana'; 'cherry'];
```

Then use function `strvcat` to vertically concatenate the two character arrays.

```
c = strvcat(c, 'watermelon');  
size (c)
```

We see that `c` is a 4 x 10 character array and spaces are automatically padded to characters that are shorter than the longest one.

```
ans =  
  
     4     10  
  
>> c  
c =  
  
     4x10 char array  
  
     'apple      '  
     'banana      '  
     'cherry       '  
     'watermelon'
```

³⁵Here character arrays are represented as “c” and string arrays “s”.

Now, we create a string array and then concatenate with another one (similarly as done above for character array `c`):

```
s = ["apple"; "banana"; "cherry"];  
s = [s; "watermelon"]
```

The result shows that `s` is a 4×1 string array:

```
s =  
  
4x1 string array  
  
"apple"  
"banana"  
"cherry"  
"watermelon"
```

Note that there are no padded spaces after short strings!

- *Cell arrays and structure arrays.* Both cell arrays and structure arrays can be used to store different types/dimensions of data that are related to one another. A cell array is built using a pair of curly braces. A structure array can be built using the **dot notation** to designate the fields of the structure, and different fields can hold different types/dimensions of data:

```
data.x = linspace(0,2*pi);  
data.y = sin(data.x);  
data.title = 'y = sin(x)'
```

The above **dot** statements define a structure array `data` with three fields, i.e., `x`, `y`, and `title`. The first two fields store numerical data while the third one stores the title of the functional relation between the two previous fields. The results shown in the command line window are:

```
data =  
  
struct with fields:  
  
x: [1x100 double]  
y: [1x100 double]  
title: 'y = sin(x)'
```


Figure 4: A sine wave generated using the first and second fields of the data structure.

The following commands plot the sine wave and give an appropriate title (Fig. 4).

```
plot(data.x,data.y)
title(data.title)
```

- *Generating vectors.* When generating vectors, colon notation can be used to reduce the use of loops. For example, `1:5` will generate array `1 2 3 4 5`. To generate a vector of numbers with a particular length, use `linspace(lo, hi, tt)`, where `lo` and `hi` are for the lower and higher limit, respectively, and `tt` is for total number of data values. Using `linspace(lo,hi)`, however, will generate 100 values.
- *Functions whose arguments are scalars, arrays and matrices* Functions whose arguments are scalars (scalar functions) can also accept arrays and matrices as arguments and return arrays or matrices after conducting entry-wise calculations. These functions include
`abs, ceil, floor, sqrt, sin cos acos, atan, log, log10, mod, round.`

Vector functions can have vectors or matrices as arguments and return the results after column-wise calculations. These include

`sum, mean, max, min, std, sort var, prod, sort, any, all.` For example, the maximum number in a matrix `A` can be obtained by `max(max(A))`.

Matrix functions have matrices as arguments. These include `eig`, `eigs`, `svd`, `det`, `size`, etc.

12.4 Matlab programming tips

- *Using Return and Continue in functions.* Let's first look at `Return` by examining two sample programs available at <https://www.mathworks.com/help/matlab/ref/return.html>:

In general, `Return` will return control from within a function to the calling program or Command line. Create a function called `findSqrRootIndex`:

```
function idx = findSqrRootIndex(target,arrayToSearch)

    idx = NaN;    % NaN = not a number
    if target < 0
        return
    end

    for idx = 1:length(arrayToSearch)
        if arrayToSearch(idx) == sqrt(target) % == is to compare for equality
            return
        end
    end
end
```

Although here in this function there is no statement to assign a value to `idx` - the output variable - it is assigned implicitly by the `for` loop: if the `idx`'th element in the input array `arrayToSearch` equals the square root of the input object `target`, the control will be returned to the calling program; at this moment `idx` takes the correct value for output - the `idx`'th element of the input array!

Now let's create a function to test the function `findSqrRootIndex()` that we created earlier.

```
function returnControlExample(target)
    arrayToSearch = [3 6 28 14 42 9 7];
    idx = findSqrRootIndex(target,arrayToSearch);

    if isnan(idx) % if idx is not a number
        disp('Square root not found.') % display a character array
    else
        disp(['Square root found at index ' num2str(idx)])
    end
end
```

At Command line, enter the following command:

```
returnControlExample(49)
```

As expected, the result is displayed:

```
Square root found at index 7
```

Here, `num2str(idx)` is to convert `idx` from a numeric data type to a character array.

Dr. Seis posted an excellent summary of `Continue` in Matlab functions at <https://www.mathworks.com/matlabcentral/answers/51298-return-and-continue-functions>. I will quote them in full:

```
function VALUE = somefunction
while SOME_CONDITION
    DO_THIS;
    if SOME_OTHER_CONDITION
        VALUE = SOMETHING;
        continue;
    end
    DO_THAT
end
DO_SOMETHING_ELSE;
```

If `SOME_OTHER_CONDITION` is true, then `continue` will skip any remaining statements (i.e., `DO_THIS` will be executed, but `DO_THAT` will be skipped) in the loop and re-enter the loop provided `SOME_CONDITION` is still true³⁶. If `SOME_OTHER_CONDITION` is false, then `continue` will not be encountered and will execute both `DO_THIS` and `DO_THAT` for that loop iteration.

- *Using persistent variables.*

12.5 Matlab graphing tips

Figure 5 can be drawn using the following commands:

³⁶As a result, here “continue” means to continue from the start of the while-loop!

Figure 5: A demonstration of Matlab’s plotting function, using x-y pairs of different lengths.

```
x = 0:0.01:2*pi;
y1 = sin(x);
plot(x,y1,'--',[0 2*pi],[0 0],':',[0 2*pi],[1 0],'-',[0 2*pi],[-1 0],'-.')
title('Plotting x-y pairs of different lengths')
xlabel 'x'
ylabel 'y'
```

In the above graph, the second x-y pair is: $[x_1 \ x_2] = [0 \ 2\pi]$, $[y_1 \ y_2] = [0 \ 0]$. To clear the contents of the active graph, use `clf`. Also note how different line types are rendered.

12.6 Cell publishing

An easy way to put together the list of a Matlab script, output of the script, as well as figures generated from running the script, into a document is Matlab’s “cell publishing” capability. The following results were generated using an example of T. A. Davis and K. Sigmon (2005)³⁷:

```
%% Integrate a function
syms x
```

³⁷T. A. Davis and K. Sigmon. 2005. MATLAB Primer. 7th Ed. Chapman & Hall/CRC. Boca Raton, Florida. USA.

```
f=x^2
e = int(f)

%%
y=sin(x)

%% Plot the results
figure (2)
ezplot(e)
```

12.6.1 Integrate a function

```
syms x
f=x^2
e = int(f)
```

```
f =
```

```
x^2
```

```
e =
```

```
x^3/3
```

```
y=sin(x)
```

```
y =
```

```
sin(x)
```

12.6.2 Plot the results

```
figure (2)
ezplot(e)
```


Note that, “%%” is used to start a cell, which is followed by the name of the cell. This name will become the name of the section automatically generated as L^AT_EX file³⁸. First we generate a symbolic variable x (note with this symbolic variable, we do not need to specify the start and end points of x).

Then, `y=sin(x)` starts the additional information to put under this same subsection (note the use of double % sign without cell title).

Note that the two lines under the section “Plot the result” generate a graph of the following function:

$$y = \frac{1}{3}x^3$$

Also note that after publishing this m-file the result is saved as a L^AT_EX file having the same name as this current m-file but under the folder called html, which is placed under the current folder. The command `figure (2)` will give the name of the displayed figure as Figure 2, but the automatically generated eps file has the name of intplt_01.eps, saved in the same folder as the L^AT_EX file intplt.tex.

³⁸With the same name of the Matlab script file generating the 2-cell example; it can also output to other types of format, such as MS Word or html.

13 Optimization through computing

13.1 Relative role of stomata on transpiration and assimilation

Cowan and Troughton (1971)³⁹ showed that, for an amphistomatous leaf, relative transpiration e and relative assimilation a of plant leaves, the ratios of instantaneous rates over rates with zero leaf resistances to water vapor and CO₂ diffusion, can be expressed as:

$$e = \frac{\epsilon r^h + r^w}{\epsilon r^h + r^w + r_l^w}, \quad (87)$$

$$a = \frac{r^c + 2r_i}{r^c + r_l^c + 2r_i}, \quad (88)$$

where r^h is boundary layer resistance to heat transfer between the leaf and the atmosphere per unit leaf area, r^w and r_l^w respectively are boundary and leaf resistance to water vapor transfer between the leaf and the atmosphere per unit leaf area, ϵ the rate of increase of latent heat content of saturated air with increase of sensible heat content, r^c , r_l^c and r_i respectively are boundary layer, leaf and internal resistances to assimilation per unit of leaf area.

After considering the ratios of various resistances, such as $r_l^w : r_l^c = 1 : 1.6$ and $r^w : r^h : r^c = 1 : 1.12 : 1.37$, Equations 87 and 88 were simplified as

$$e = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{r_l^c/r^c}{1.31\epsilon + 1.17}}, \quad (89)$$

$$a = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{r_l^c/r^c}{2r_i/r^c + 1}}. \quad (90)$$

A further simplification led to a relationship between e and a :

$$e = \frac{a}{\alpha + (1 - \alpha)a}, \quad (91)$$

where

$$\alpha = \frac{r_i/r^c + k_1}{0.66\epsilon + k_2}, \quad (92)$$

where $k_1 = 0.5$ and $k_2 = 0.58$ for amphistomatous leaves, and $k_1 = 1$ and $k_2 = 1.17$ for hypostomatous leaves.

Cowan and Troughton (1971) suggested using equation $r^c = 3.4(b/u)^{1/2}$ to evaluate r^c , where b is leaf breadth (cm) and u wind speed (cm/s). They also provided a graphical illustration of ϵ as a function of temperature T in their Fig. 1, which can be approximated by a quadratic equation $\epsilon = 0.6649 + 0.0226T + 0.00258T^2$.

³⁹I. R. Cowan and J. H. Troughton. 1971. The relative role of stomata in transpiration and assimilation. *Planta*. 97: 325–336.

Figure 6: Transpiration ratio in relation to relative assimilation rate for amphistomatous leaves of C_3 and C_4 plants with different sizes under different environmental conditions. In generating this figure, the values of the nine variables/parameters suggested in macro CT_1971.mac were used.

Figure 7: Same as Figure 6 except that the value of a_{oh} was changed to 1 (for hypostomatous leaves).

Using equations 91 and 92, I tried to generate a visual appreciation for practical implications of Cowan and Troughton's model. The calculation was done using a MINITAB macro (Appendix 15.11) and the results are shown in Figures 6 and 7. This exercise also demonstrates some of the graphics capabilities of MINITAB.

13.2 Dynamic optimization

In this category of optimization tool, Some hypothetical production process is assumed to be accomplished in several stages⁴⁰ as shown in Figure 8. At the beginning the product is in state A . After going through several stages the final state Z is obtained. In each of the stages, there are different pathways to process the product, and each of the pathways is assigned a number (cost in dollars). The manufacture's objective is to find a particular time path of the production process, so as to minimize the total cost. For the simple situation as described in Fig.1a, American mathematician R. E. Bellman's [Principle of Optimality](#) can be used. This principle states that, the optimized solution of this kind can be obtained in a backward direction. That is, first we start from last stage, path JZ has the least cost (1 dollar). So for the last stage the optimized solution is path JZ . Once the last stage is settled, the penultimate stage will have to be selected from two possibilities: between path GJ and path HJ . Apparently, the cost associated with path HJ is lower. So, the optimal solution for the 4th stage is HJ . According to the Principle of Optimality, in this situation, the optimal solution for the last two stages (4-5) must contain the optimal solution of the last stage (stage 5). So the path HJZ is the optimal solution for the last two stages. Applying this same method to the remaining stages, the optimal solution to the whole production process becomes path $ACEHJZ$, with a total cost of 14 dollars.

An important implication of the example in Figure 8 is that the optimal solution of the whole production process may not be obtained by summing the optimal solution obtained individually at each of the production stages. For example, in the first stage, although path AB involves less cost (2 dollars), the optimal time path for the whole production period, however, goes through path AC , which is more costly (4 dollars) when compared with path AB .

There might be an analogy between the situation of Figure 8 and the process of animal production. If we could simplify the production stages in a similar fashion, then we could use this method to figure out the optimal (minimum) time path of cost. If, on the other hand, our purpose is to find the maximum of something, we can follow the same procedure, but at each stage we choose the highest path value available. More examples in agriculture can be found from here. ⁴¹. The following example (France and Thornley, 1984. P 267) can be formulated using the framework of dynamic programming.

[A sheep farmer starts off with a flock of \$k\$ sheep. At the end of each year, over the next](#)

⁴⁰This figure is redrawn according to Alpha Chiang, 2000, Elements of Dynamic Optimization. Waveland Press, Illinois

⁴¹France J. and Thornley, J.H.M., 1984. Mathematical Models in Agriculture: A Quantitative Approach to Problems in Agriculture and Related Sciences. Butterworth and Co (Publishers) Ltd. England. Pages 63-66, 267, 292-293, 311

Figure 8: (a): Discrete situation of the dynamic programming problem. The optimal time path is in cyan (left). (b): A graphical representation of solution to a linear programming problem (right). The final optimal solution can be efficiently approached if, given an initial starting point, a minimum of number of steps are followed before the optimal point is identified.

N years, he has to decide how many sheep to sell and how many to keep. If he sells, his profit on a sheep is r_n [£] in year n . If he keeps, the number of sheep kept in year n will be doubled in year $n + 1$. The farmer intends to sell completely at the end of N years.

13.3 Linear programming

The problem of linear programming (LP) is to find an optimum (minimum or maximum) of an *objective function*, expressed in *linear* form in relation to several *original variables*, subject to one or more linear *constraints*. The constraints can be of equality type, or inequality (greater than or less than) type. The solution of LP problem is due to George Dantzig as published in 1963 as *the Simplex method*. Here we will use a True BASIC program, OPTLP⁴², by Hanna and Sandall (1995)⁴³ to solve basic LP problems. Although the calculations are carried out automatically by the computer program, we need to understand what's going on during the calculation process. To this end, we now review several important characteristics of a typical LP problem.

First we write a sample LP problem as

$$\text{Minimize } z = 4x_1 - 2x_2 - x_3$$

⁴²A Fortran version of the program was also provided by the authors.

⁴³Hanna O.T. and Sandall O.C., 1995. Computational Methods in Chemical Engineering, Prentice Hall PTR, Upper Saddle River, New Jersey.

Subject to

$$3x_1 + 4x_2 - x_3 \leq 1 \tag{93}$$

$$-2x_1 + 10x_2 + 7x_3 \leq 3$$

This sample problem is due to Hanna and Sandall (1995). For typical LP problems, the values of all the *original* variables, namely, x_1, x_2, \dots , have to be *positive*. If some of them are not positive, new variables have to be introduced to make the resultant *new* LP problem containing *only* positive original variables. Also the RHS (right-hand side) for all the constraints have to be positive. If they are not originally positive, the constraints can be multiplied by -1 and the inequality signs be reversed.

A hypothetical LP problem and its solution strategy are illustrated geometrically in Figure 8b. Here, for the LP problem, the constraints form a *convex* set, and the solution of the *linear programming*, if exists, lies only on one of the *corners* of the convex set (case of unique solution), or along a line (case of non-unique solutions)⁴⁴. For the case shown in Figure 8b, there are only 2 original variables, x_1 and x_2 . As a result, the objective function $z = f(x_1, x_2)$ corresponds to lines in the x_1 - x_2 plane, if the value of z is determined. The ultimate aim is to locate a pair of x_1 and x_2 , so that an optimal value of the objective function is obtained. For convenience, let's only use *minimum* for optimization, because any *maximum* objective function can be transposed into a minimum problem by minimizing the *minus* of the original maximizing objective function.

Let's return to Figure 8b and describe the solution procedure of the LP problem intuitively. Suppose, from some kind of mathematical analysis, we know that the solution of this LP problem lies in one of 5 corners of the convex set as shown in Figure 8b. Then we just need to try the 5 points one by one to see which can lead to the minimization of the objective function. These 5 points are called *feasible* points, meaning that the optimal point has to be chosen from these candidate points. One method is to evaluate the objective function exhaustively at all 5 points and choose the point having the minimum objective function value. This exhaustive searching method is not efficient especially when there are many points to be evaluated. In the simplex method, however, the searching progresses more efficiently toward the final optimal point. Assume first we start with point *A*. After the objective function is evaluated at this point, a test is used to determine if this is the optimal point. If it is, the search process stops here. If, for example, by evaluating the objective function, there is still possibility to decrease the value of the objective function further, then the search moves on. The next point at which to evaluate the objective function is chosen such that the objective function is decreased most. For small problems, the searching process would reach the final optimal point in only a few steps.

Next we will see how the simplex method solve the LP problem by using the sample problem as of Eqn (93). We first assume that the problem only has LT (less than) type of constraints. For problems having other types (equal to or greater than) of constraints, some

⁴⁴For non-linear programming, the solution may be found in the interior of the convex set

pre-calculations are required but the fundamental method used is similar to the one we will describe now. In Eqn (93), we need to introduce 2 new variables, here called *slack* variables, x_4 and x_5 , so that all the LT constraints now are changed into equalities, as shown in Eqn (94).

$$4x_1 - 2x_2 - x_3 = z \quad (94a)$$

$$3x_1 + 4x_2 - x_3 + x_4 = 1 \quad (94b)$$

$$-2x_1 + 10x_2 + 7x_3 + x_5 = 3 \quad (94c)$$

The slack variables x_4 and x_5 are called *basic variables* for the now equality constraints to which they belong, while other variables, x_1 , x_2 and x_3 are called *non-basic variables*⁴⁵. For this type of LP problem, the simplex method first *solves for* the basic variables assuming all the non-basic variables equal to zero. In this case, we have $x_4 = 1$, and $x_5 = 3$. Since the non-basic variables $x_1 = x_2 = x_3 = 0$, the objective function now has the value of zero. So far we have got the first *basic feasible solution* to the original LP problem.

Next is to determine if there is a possibility to further decrease the objective function by exchanging one of the non-basic variables with one of the basic variables, and solving for the new basic variables, as well as updating the value of the objective function. Hanna and Sandall (1995) explained clearly how to do this (see page 205 of their text). After considering both feasibility and optimality, they ended up deciding to exchange the current non-basic variable x_2 with the basic variable x_4 , resulting in the updated basic variables being x_2 and x_5 , and non-basic variables x_1 , x_3 , and x_4 . As illustrated in Fox et al. (1987), in computer the matrix arithmetic is used to carry out the solving-substitution calculations, which are extremely useful when the problem becomes larger and hand-calculation is time-consuming and error-prone.⁴⁶ Using the method of Fox et al. (1987), we now explain the further steps of solving our sample problem.

To conduct matrix calculation, we now introduce another variable, x_6 , into the objective function and write the objective function following the two equality constraints as follows.

$$3x_1 + 4x_2 - x_3 + x_4 + 0x_5 + 0x_6 = 1 \quad (95a)$$

$$-2x_1 + 10x_2 + 7x_3 + 0x_4 + x_5 + 0x_6 = 3 \quad (95b)$$

$$4x_1 - 2x_2 - x_3 + 0x_4 + 0x_5 + x_6 = 0 \quad (95c)$$

Now there are 3 rather than 2 basic variables in Eqn (95), namely, x_4 , x_5 , and x_6 . From the previous analysis, we know that we want exchange x_2 with one of the current basic variables, x_4 . The variable x_6 is totally a “dummy” variable introduced just in order to

⁴⁵As seen in the discussion of Hanna and Sandall (1995), pages 203, these basic variables are also called the “solved-for” variables. In the discussion of Fox et al. (1987), however, the basic variables are called “dependent variables”, while the non-basic variables are called “arbitrary variables.”

⁴⁶Fox W.P., Giodano F.R., Maddox S.L., Weir M.D., 1987, *Mathematical Modeling with MINITAB*. Brooks/Cole Publishing Company, Monterey, California.

conduct some matrix calculations, and it is not to be considered as a candidate of a new non-basic variable. It is always a basic variable and we will see later it will hold the value of the objective function z at the end of the simplex calculation. First we use the coefficients of the new basic variables (x_2 , x_5 , and x_6) to form matrix A_1

$$A_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 4 & 0 & 0 \\ 10 & 1 & 0 \\ -2 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (96)$$

and use the coefficients of Eqn (95), including the RHS (with a value 0 for z , because z is undetermined and its value will be stored in x_6), to form A_2 .

$$A_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 3 & 4 & -1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ -2 & 10 & 7 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 3 \\ 4 & -2 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (97)$$

Now pre-multiply A_2 by the inverse of A_1 , e.g., A_1^{-1} . This will complete the variable exchange, with x_2 now becoming a basic variable and x_4 now is a non-basic variable.

$$A_3 = \begin{pmatrix} 0.75 & 1 & -0.25 & 0.25 & 0 & 0 & 0.25 \\ -9.5 & 0 & 9.5 & -2.5 & 1 & 0 & 0.5 \\ 5.5 & 0 & -1.5 & 0.5 & 0 & 1 & 0.5 \end{pmatrix} \quad (98)$$

With this updated coefficient matrix, the original Eqn (94) now is changed into

$$5.5x_1 - 1.5x_3 + 0.5x_4 - 0.5 = z \quad (99a)$$

$$0.75x_1 + x_2 - 0.25x_3 + 0.25x_4 = 0.25 \quad (99b)$$

$$-9.5x_1 + 9.5x_3 - 2.5x_4 + x_5 = 0.5 \quad (99c)$$

Note the objective function z now has the value of -0.5 (rather than 0), indicating the change of variable indeed improved the objective function. Also note that the values for the original and slack variables are $x_1 = 0$, $x_2 = 0.25$, $x_3 = 0$, $x_4 = 0$, and $x_5 = 0.5$. Compare these with the results of Hanna and Sandall (1995), who exchanged variables through manual substitution and solving (see Eqn (c) on page 206 of their text).

Since there is still a negative coefficient in the updated objective function (-1.5 for x_3 in Eqn 99a), there is still room to further decrease the objective function by increasing x_3 . In Eqn 99b, the value x_3 can become -1 if x_2 is set to zero. But this will violate the non-negativity of x_3 . So we could not exchange x_3 with the current basic variable x_2 . Looking at Eqn 99c, the value of x_3 becomes 0.3 if x_5 is set to zero. So, we will exchange x_3 with the current basic variable x_5 . The updated basic variables will now become x_2 and x_3 . We now use the coefficients of the new basic variables (x_2 , x_3 , and x_6) from matrix A_3 to form matrix A_4

$$A_4 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -0.25 & 0 \\ 0 & 9.5 & 0 \\ 0 & -1.5 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (100)$$

Table 8: Nutrition requirements of an average size horse.

Feed stuff	Protein (lb)	Carbohydrates (lb)	Roughage (lb)	Cost (Dollars)
Hay/bale	0.5	2.0	5.0	1.80
Oats/sack	1.0	4.0	2.0	3.50
Feeding blocks/block	2.0	0.5	1.0	0.40
High-protein concentrate/sack	6.0	1.0	2.5	1.00
Requirements/horse/week	40.0	20.0	45.0	

Now pre-multiply A_3 by the inverse of A_4 , e.g., A_4^{-1} . This will complete the variable exchange, with x_3 now becoming a basic variable and x_5 a non-basic variable. The updated coefficient matrix becomes:

$$A_5 = \begin{pmatrix} 0.5 & 1 & 0 & 0.184211 & 0.026316 & 0 & 0.263158 \\ -1.0 & 0 & 1 & -0.263158 & 0.105263 & 0 & 0.052632 \\ 4.0 & 0 & 0 & 0.105263 & 0.157895 & 1 & 0.578947 \end{pmatrix} \quad (101)$$

With this updated coefficient matrix, the original Eqn (94) now is changed into

$$4.0x_1 + 0.105263x_4 + 0.157895x_5 - 0.578947 = z \quad (102a)$$

$$0.5x_1 + x_2 + 0.184211x_4 + 0.026316x_5 = 0.263158 \quad (102b)$$

$$-1.0x_1 + x_3 - 0.263158x_4 + 0.105263x_5 = 0.052632 \quad (102c)$$

Now since there is no more negative coefficient in the objective function, the updated value of the objective function $z = -0.578947$ is the optimal solution to the original LP problem Eqn 93, and the original variables leading to this optimal solution are: $x_1 = 0$, $x_2 = 0.263158$, and $x_3 = 0.052632$ ($x_4 = x_5 = 0$). Using program OPTLP, Hanna and Sandall (1995) obtained the same final solution for this problem (see pages 206-207 of their text). In our demonstration, the solving-substitution calculations were done using a Minitab macro (see Appendix 15.12).

For more complex problems, it is recommended to use some specialized LP solvers. Now let's solve a practical LP problem for animal rationing using the program OPTLP by Hanna and Sandall (1995). This is the Exercise 2 in Chapter 8 of Fox et al. (1987):

A rancher has determined that the minimum weekly nutritional requirement for an average size horse include 40 lb of protein, 20 lb of carbohydrates, and 45 lb of roughage. These are obtained from the following sources in varying amounts at the given prices, as shown in Table 8. Formulate a mathematical model to determine how to meet the minimum nutritional requirement at minimum cost.

Solution. Assume the farmer is going to use x_1 bales of hay, x_2 sacks of oats, x_3 blocks of feeding blocks and x_4 sacks of high-protein concentrate. We formulate the model as a LP problem,

$$\text{Minimize } z = 1.8x_1 + 3.5x_2 + 0.4x_3 + x_4$$

Subject to

$$0.5x_1 + x_2 + 2x_3 + 6x_4 \geq 40 \tag{103}$$

$$2x_1 + 4x_2 + 0.5x_3 + x_4 \geq 20$$

$$5x_1 + 2x_2 + x_3 + 2.5x_4 \geq 45$$

$$x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4 \geq 0$$

Run program OPTLP and we find: $z_{opt} = 17$, $x_1 = 5$, $x_2 = 0$, $x_3 = 20$, $x_4 = 0$. So the optimal cost of the weekly horse feedstuff is 17 dollars, with 5 bales of hay and 20 feeding blocks but without using any of oats or high-protein concentrate. Formulation of this problem assumes we have had enough previous knowledge about animal nutrient requirements. This is usually available, at least approximately for experienced managers. If, however, the price of one or more feedstuff changes, we can re-run the model with the changed price(s) as the new input, and get the updated optimal solution to the problem. Other possibilities can also be tried using this model. For example, if there is a limited supply of feeding blocks and the maximum amount available to this farm per week is 10 blocks, then we have to add an additional *supply constraint* of feeding blocks to the problem formulation, and re-run the model to get an optimized solution. We can imagine that, if other aspects of the model keep unchanged, then the new optimal solution might have to include the more expensive oats or high-protein concentrate in order to satisfy the minimum weekly requirement of horse, which might increase the weekly cost (current optimal cost is 17 dollars) somewhat.

We can use this computer program of linear programming as a “calculator” to deal with other, probably larger, problems.

Now we add a couple of lines on the use of this program. The users are required to provide data to the subroutine *Init*. These are:

- N , number of original variables.
- M , total number of inequality/equation constraints.
- GT , number of ‘greater than’ inequality constraints.
- EQ , number of ‘equal to’ constraints.
- LT , number of ‘less than’ inequality constraints.
- $A(i, j)$, coefficients of the constraints. These only include the left-hand side coefficients, row by row. First enter all the ‘greater than’ coefficients, followed by ‘equal to’ coefficients, and last the ‘less than’ coefficients.

- $b(i)$, column vector of the right-hand side of the coefficients, in the same order from GT , to EQ , and then to LT .
- $c(j)$, row vector of the coefficients of the objective function.

For the final output, if an unique solution is found (sometimes there can be no solution, either due to inconsistencies in the constraints, or other aspects of the problem formulation), we can see the basic variables selected for the final iteration are printed along with the final value for z . The non-basic variables (including the ones that were originally the basic variables at the start of the problem) have the value of zero.

13.4 Dealing with unrestricted variables

Solving an LP problem using program OPTLP requires the constraints to be specified either of (\geq), (\leq) or ($=$) type with all variables being non-negative. In case a variable, say x_1 , is unrestricted in sign, it will be represented by two non-negative variables such that $x_1 = x_1^- - x_1^+$. In any step of the LP computation, x_1 can only take one of the following three values:

$$x_1 = \begin{cases} x_1^- & \text{if } x_1^+ = 0, \\ x_1^+ & \text{if } x_1^- = 0, \\ 0 & \text{if } x_1^-, x_1^+ = 0. \end{cases}$$

This means that x_1^- and x_1^+ cannot be positive at the same time, or, in other words, at any step of the LP computation, if one of them is included in the list of the basic variables, then the other must be in the list of the non-basic variables. This also means that, when finding out the corner point formed by x_1 and another variable, say x_2 , only one possible combination, either of (x_1^-, x_2) or (x_1^+, x_2) , is a valid corner point, signifying either x_1 is positive, or negative, but not simultaneously positive *and* negative. Let's discuss about this important point further by solving an LP problem from Taha (2007)⁴⁷:

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{Maximize } z = x_1 + 3x_2 \\ & \text{Subject to} \\ & x_1 + x_2 \leq 2 \\ & -x_1 + x_2 \leq 4 \\ & x_1 \text{ unrestricted, } x_2 \geq 0 \end{aligned} \tag{104}$$

First let's convert above problem into equation form and find out the feasible and non-feasible corner points. Since the two constraints are of the \leq -type, we add one slack variable to each of the inequalities to form equation constraints:

⁴⁷Problem Set 3.2A, Exercise 5

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{Maximize } z = x_1 + 3x_2 + 0y_1 + 0y_2 \\
& \text{Subject to} \\
& \quad x_1 + x_2 + y_1 = 2 \\
& \quad -x_1 + x_2 + y_2 = 4 \\
& \quad x_1 \text{ unrestricted, } x_2, y_1, y_2 \geq 0
\end{aligned} \tag{105}$$

Since we have two equations and four variables, we have $C_2^4 = 6$ corner points to evaluate⁴⁸ for an optimal solution of the objective function. Also, to deal with the unrestricted nature of x_1 , we convert Eqn. 105 into the following form before enumerating all corner points:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{Maximize } z = x_1^- - x_1^+ + 3x_2 + 0y_1 + 0y_2 \\
& \text{Subject to} \\
& \quad x_1^- - x_1^+ + x_2 + y_1 = 2, \\
& \quad -x_1^- + x_1^+ + x_2 + y_2 = 4 \\
& \quad x_1^-, x_1^+, x_2, y_1, y_2 \geq 0
\end{aligned} \tag{106}$$

Through manual substitution and solving, we collected all combinations of basic variables and non-basic variables in Table 9. It can be verified that the corner point at (0, 4) is not a feasible point, because it does not satisfy the first constraint of Eqn. 106. At the same time, the basic solution for y_1 is negative at that point. It can also be seen from Table 9 that negative basic solutions were obtained for all of the invalid choices of x_1^- , or x_1^+ .

To verify the above hand-calculated results, let's solve the LP problem using the True BASIC program OPTLP. We first replace the unrestricted variable x_1 in Eqn. 104 with two non-negative variables x_1^- and x_1^+ , and also, convert the maximization problem into an minimization one, resulting in a problem with three variables (x_1^- , x_1^+ and x_2) and two inequality constraints:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{Minimize } z = -x_1^- + x_1^+ - 3x_2 \\
& \text{Subject to} \\
& \quad x_1^- - x_1^+ + x_2 \leq 2 \\
& \quad -x_1^- + x_1^+ + x_2 \leq 4 \\
& \quad x_1^-, x_1^+, x_2 \geq 0
\end{aligned} \tag{107}$$

⁴⁸For an LP problem with n variables and m constraints, there are C_m^n corner points to evaluate. Thus for moderate to large LP problems, the more efficient *Simplex* method, instead of the exhaustive searching method, is used.

Table 9: A list all possible combinations of basic/non-basic variables and associated corner points for the solution of Eqn. 106. The boldface letters represent the corner points labeled with the same letters in Fig. 9.

Non-basic variables	Basic variables	Basic solution	Coordinates of corner point (x_1 - x_2)	Feasible?	Objective Function value
(x_1^+, y_1, y_2)	(x_1^-, x_2)	$(-1, 3)$	-	-	-
(x_1^-, y_1, y_2)	(x_1^+, x_2)	$(1, 3)$	D $(-1, 3)$	Yes	8
(x_1^+, x_2, y_2)	(x_1^-, y_1)	$(-4, 6)$	-	-	-
(x_1^-, x_2, y_2)	(x_1^+, y_1)	$(4, 6)$	C $(-4, 0)$	Yes	-4
(x_1^-, x_2, y_1)	(x_1^+, y_2)	$(-2, 6)$	-	-	-
(x_1^+, x_2, y_1)	(x_1^-, y_2)	$(2, 6)$	A $(2, 0)$	Yes	2
(x_1^-, x_1^+, y_2)	(x_2, y_1)	$(4, -2)$	F $(0, 4)$	No	-
(x_1^-, x_1^+, y_1)	(x_2, y_2)	$(2, 2)$	E $(0, 2)$	Yes	6
(x_1^-, x_1^+, x_2)	(y_1, y_2)	$(2, 4)$	B $(0, 0)$	Yes	0

Figure 9: Graphical solution of Eqn. 106. All of the six corner points are feasible except for point **F**. The optimal solution of the objective function ($z = 8$) is obtained at point **D**, where $x_1 = -1$ and $x_2 = 3$.

The outputs from OPTLP are shown below:

```

-----
Basic Var.  Value
   4         2
   5         4
   z         0

Var.j  =  1     2     3     4     5
A(1,j)  1    -1     1     *     0
A(2,j) -1     1     1     0     *
z       = -1     1    -3     *     *
-----

```

Variable to enter basis is S = 3
Pivot at row 1, column 3

```

Basic Var.  Value
   3         2
   5         2
   z        -6

Var.j  =  1     2     3     4     5
A(1,j)  1    -1     *     1     0
A(2,j) -2     2     0    -1     *
z       =  2    -2     *     3     *
-----

```

Variable to enter basis is S = 2
Pivot at row 2, column 2

Final Solution Results...

```

Basic Var.  Value
   3         3
   2         1
   z        -8

Var.j  =  1     2     3     4     5
A(1,j)  0     0     *    .5    .5
A(2,j) -1     *     0   -.5    .5
z       =  0     *     *     2     1
-----

```

The above results indicate that OPTLP evaluated three corner points⁴⁹ to solve Eqn. 107. First it evaluated point **B**, then **E** and finally obtained optimal solution at **D**. To convert back to the maximization problem, we see that the optimal solution to Eqn. 104

⁴⁹Note that variables x_1^- and x_1^+ take places at $j = 1$, and $j = 2$ respectively in the output table from OPTLP.

is $z = 8$ obtained at point $(x_1 = -1, x_2 = 3)$ ⁵⁰, which is the same as the hand-calculated results shown in Table 9 and Figure 9.

As discussed in Taha (2007), for an LP problem with m unrestricted variables, instead using $2 \times m$ non-negative variables, we can use $m + 1$ non-negative variables to represent the original m unrestricted variables. For example, if both x_1 and x_2 are unrestricted, we can let $x_1 = x'_1 - w$ and $x_2 = x'_2 - w$, thus using only 3 variables (instead of 4). Let's demonstrate this point by solving an LP problem by Taha (2007)⁵¹:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \text{Maximize} \quad z = -2x_1 + 3x_2 - 2x_3 \\
 & \text{Subject to} \\
 & \quad 4x_1 - x_2 - 5x_3 = 10 \\
 & \quad 2x_1 + 3x_2 + 2x_3 = 12 \\
 & \quad x_1 \geq 0, x_2, x_3 \text{ unrestricted.}
 \end{aligned} \tag{108}$$

Let's formulate the above problem in two ways and demonstrate using OPTLP that both have the same results. First, let's use the relation $x_j = x_j^- - x_j^+$, $j = 2, 3$, to rewrite Eqn. 108⁵²:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \text{Minimize} \quad z' = 2x_1 - 3x_2^- + 3x_2^+ + 2x_3^- - 2x_3^+ \\
 & \text{Subject to} \\
 & \quad 4x_1 - x_2^- + x_2^+ - 5x_3^- + 5x_3^+ = 10 \\
 & \quad 2x_1 + 3x_2^- - 3x_2^+ + 2x_3^- - 2x_3^+ = 12 \\
 & \quad x_1, x_2^-, x_2^+, x_3^-, x_3^+ \geq 0
 \end{aligned} \tag{109}$$

After providing the appropriate coefficients of the above LP problem to OPTLP, we obtained the following minimization solution: $z' = -24.92308$, $x_1 = 0$, $x_2^- = 6.1538$, $x_2^+ = 0$, $x_3^- = 0$, $x_3^+ = 3.2308$. Changing back to our original maximization LP problem (Eqn. 108), we have $z = 24.92308$, $x_1 = 0$, $x_2 = x_2^- - x_2^+ = 6.1538$, $x_3 = x_3^- - x_3^+ = -3.2308$.

Next we will show that the alternative formulation ($x_j = x'_j - w, j = 2, 3$) will yield the same optimal solution. Again we will first need to convert the original problem into a minimization problem (to meet the requirements of OPTLP):

⁵⁰For Eqn. 107, the maximal z value corresponds to the point $(x_1^- = 0, x_1^+ = 1, x_2 = 3)$.

⁵¹This is Exercise 4 from Problem Set 3.1B

⁵²We also convert the original problem into a minimization problem by taking the negative of the objective function.

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{Minimize} && z' = 2x_1 - 3x'_2 + 2x'_3 + w \\
& && \text{Subject to} \\
& && 4x_1 - x'_2 - 5x'_3 + 6w = 10 \\
& && 2x_1 + 3x'_2 + 2x'_3 - 5w = 12 \\
& && x_1, x'_2, x'_3, w \geq 0
\end{aligned} \tag{110}$$

Using OPTLP, we obtained the following minimization solution: $z' = -24.92308$, $x_1 = 0$, $x'_2 = 9.3846$, $x'_3 = 0$, $w = 3.2308$. Changing back to our original maximization LP problem (Eqn. 108), we have $z = 24.92308$, $x_1 = 0$, $x_2 = x'_2 - w = 6.1538$, and $x_3 = x'_3 - w = -3.2308$. As expected, the results indeed are the same as those obtained from the first formulation (i.e., Eqn. 109).

13.5 Duality in Linear programming

An LP problem with n decision (or original) variables and m constraints in its equation form⁵³ can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{Minimize} && z = \sum_{j=1}^n c_j x_j \\
& && \text{Subject to} \\
& && \sum_{j=1}^n a_{ij} x_j = b_i, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, m \\
& && x_j \geq 0 \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, n.
\end{aligned} \tag{111}$$

A *dual* LP problem corresponding to Eqn 111 as the *primal* form can be formulated to have m original variables and n constraints:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{Maximize} && w = \sum_{k=1}^m b_k y_k \\
& && \text{Subject to} \\
& && \sum_{k=1}^m a_{kj} y_k \leq c_j, \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, n \\
& && y_1, y_2, \dots, y_m \geq 0
\end{aligned} \tag{112}$$

⁵³Constraints with inequalities can be converted to equalities by adding slack or artificial variables as needed in order to form a system of equations.

To formulate the above dual problem, the *sense*⁵⁴ of the LP problem, namely, maximization or minimization, as well as the nature of the constraints (\leq , \geq , or $=$), need to be changed. For example, according to Taha (2007), if the original LP problem is a minimization problem, the dual form must be a maximization problem, and *vice versa*; if the dual form is a maximization problem, the inequality constraints must be \leq type, and if it is a minimization problem, then the inequality constraints must be \geq type. An important property of the duality of LP is that, if the primal LP problem has an optimal solution for its objective function, this same optimal solution is also the optimal solution of its dual LP problem. One application of this property is in data envelopment analysis (DEA) of production efficiency⁵⁵, in which the use of the dual form can significantly increase the computing efficiency for some large LP problems.

As an exercise, let's formulate our sample LP problem into the dual form and solve it using program OPTLP by Hanna and Sanddle (1996) to verify that the same optimal solution obtained in the primal LP problem, i.e., the minimum of the objective function is $z = -0.578947$, can be achieved for this dual problem.

Let's re-write our minimization problem in Eqns 93 and 94 in equation form with two slack variables x_4 and x_5 :

$$\begin{aligned} 4x_1 - 2x_2 - x_3 + 0x_4 + 0x_5 &= z \\ 3x_1 + 4x_2 - x_3 + x_4 &= 1 \\ -2x_1 + 10x_2 + 7x_3 + x_5 &= 3 \end{aligned} \tag{113}$$

Using the rules summarized by Taha (2007), the dual LP problem is formulated as:

$$\begin{aligned} & \textit{Maximize} \quad w = y_1 + 3y_2 \\ & \textit{Subject to} \\ & 3y_1 - 2y_2 \leq 4 \\ & 4y_1 + 10y_2 \leq -2 \\ & -y_1 + 7y_2 \leq -1 \\ & y_1 \leq 0 \\ & y_2 \leq 0 \end{aligned} \tag{114}$$

Since program OPTLP requires that all of the original variables are non-negative, and the LP problem should be in minimization format, we multiply both sides of the objective function and all constraints to obtain:

⁵⁴See H. A. Taha. 2007. Operations Research: An Introduction. 8th Ed. Pearson Education Inc., Upper Saddle River, New Jersey, USA. Pages 151-153.

⁵⁵R. Ramanathan. 2003. An Introduction to Data Envelopment Analysis - A Tool for Performance Measurement. Sage Publications India Pvt Ltd., New Delhi.

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{Minimize} && -w = -y_1 - 3y_2 \\
& \text{Subject to} && \\
& && -3y_1 + 2y_2 \geq -4 \\
& && -4y_1 - 10y_2 \geq 2 \\
& && y_1 - 7y_2 \geq 1 \\
& && -y_1 \geq 0 \\
& && -y_2 \geq 0
\end{aligned} \tag{115}$$

Now let $w' = -w$, and $y'_i = -y_i$, Eqn 115 becomes

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{Minimize} && w' = y'_1 + 3y'_2 \\
& \text{Subject to} && \\
& && 3y'_1 - 2y'_2 \geq -4 \\
& && 4y'_1 + 10y'_2 \geq 2 \\
& && -y'_1 + 7y'_2 \geq 1 \\
& && y'_1 \geq 0 \\
& && y'_2 \geq 0
\end{aligned} \tag{116}$$

Now we will need to fix one more thing in Eqn 116: that is, to multiply both sides of the first inequality by -1 so its RHS becomes positive, which is also required by OPTLP. With that change, as well as place the new \leq constraint after two \geq constraints, our dual LP problem, which now has two original variables and three constraints, becomes:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{Minimize} && w' = y'_1 + 3y'_2 \\
& \text{Subject to} && \\
& && 4y'_1 + 10y'_2 \geq 2 \\
& && -y'_1 + 7y'_2 \geq 1 \\
& && -3y'_1 + 2y'_2 \leq 4 \\
& && y'_1, y'_2 \geq 0
\end{aligned} \tag{117}$$

After providing the appropriate coefficients of Eqn 117 to OPTLP, we ran the program and obtained the following output results:

Final Solution Results...

Basic Var.	Value
1	.105263
2	.157895
5	4
z	.578947

Var. j =	1	2	3	4	5
A(1, j)	*	0	-.184211	.263158	0
A(2, j)	0	*	-.0263158	-.105263	0
A(3, j)	0	0	-.5	1.0	*
z	*	*	.263158	.0526316	*

The above results indicate that the final minimization solution for Eqn 117 is $w' = 0.578947$, which is achieved when the original variables take values of $y'_1 = 0.105263$ and $y'_2 = 0.157895$. After changing back to variables of our dual LP problem, Eqn 114, we have the maximization solution of $w = -0.578947$, which is achieved when the original variables take values of $y_1 = -0.105263$ and $y_2 = -0.157895$. We see that the final optimization result from this dual LP problem indeed is identical to that of the primal LP problem (i.e., Eqn 93)!

13.6 Further notes on optimization-related concepts

As detailed in Hanna and Sandall (1995), there are other important points in basic optimization that are useful for scientific applications.

- **Necessary and sufficient conditions for the optimums of simple functions.**

In college calculus class, we were taught that the necessary (sufficient) conditions for a local optimum of a one-variable function can be obtained by evaluating the first (second) derivatives. For a function $y = f(x)$, if $y' = 0$ and $y'' > 0$ at some point, then y has a local minimum at this point; if, on the other hand, $y' = 0$ and $y'' < 0$, then y has a local maximum at this point. Either of these two possibilities happen most of the time. However, if the first and second derivatives both equal to zero at some point of interest, we have to pursue further to get an answer.

When $f(x)$ has a *stationary point*, it can be a maximum, a minimum, or a saddle point. Suppose from this stationary point, x is *perturbed* to a very small amount, Δx . The function $f(x)$ has a maximum (minimum) if $\Delta f < 0$ ($\Delta f > 0$). The function has a saddle point if the sign of Δf is not determined. In calculus, a stationary point always has $dy/dx = 0$. Suppose $f(x)$ has a stationary point at point x^* , and we now use Taylor Theorem to expand $f(x)$ at point x^* . Define a small change of x as $h = x - x^*$, then we have,

$$\begin{aligned}
f(x) - f(x^*) &= \Delta f \\
&= \left(\frac{dy}{dx}\right)_{x^*} \cdot h + \left(\frac{d^2y}{dx^2}\right)_{x^*} \cdot \frac{h^2}{2!} + \left(\frac{d^3y}{dx^3}\right)_{x^*} \cdot \frac{h^3}{3!} + \dots
\end{aligned} \tag{118}$$

If $f(x)$ has a maximum or minimum at point x^* (e.g., Δf has definite *sign*, negative or positive, at this point), then $\left(\frac{dy}{dx}\right)_{x^*}$ in Eqn (118) must equal to zero, otherwise, the sign of Δf can not be determined, because it can be changed depending whether h is positive or negative. So, $\left(\frac{dy}{dx}\right)_{x^*} = 0$ is the necessary condition of local optimum at point x^* . For sufficient condition of local optimum, we have to look at the higher order terms in Eqn(118). If $\left(\frac{d^2y}{dx^2}\right)_{x^*} \neq 0$, then $f(x)$ has a maximum if $\left(\frac{d^2y}{dx^2}\right)_{x^*} < 0$, and minimum if $\left(\frac{d^2y}{dx^2}\right)_{x^*} > 0$. But if $\left(\frac{d^2y}{dx^2}\right)_{x^*} = 0$, we have to check the higher order non-zero term, e.g., $\left(\frac{d^3y}{dx^3}\right)_{x^*}$. If this term does not equal to zero, because now it is the leading term, the sign of Δf can not be uniform, it can be positive or negative depending on the actual sign of h . So, $f(x)$ has saddle point at x^* . In general, if the non-zero leading term is in the *odd* position, then $f(x)$ has saddle point at x^* ; if the non-zero leading term is in the *even* position, then $f(x)$ has an optimum: it has maximum if the leading derivative is negative, and a minimum if the derivative is positive.

- **Lagrange multiplier** This is useful in solving some of the equality-constrained optimization problems.
- **Kuhn-Tucker condition** This, partly based on the Lagrange multiplier, is useful for solving some of the non-linear programming (NLP) problems.
- **Direct search method** The authors (Hanna and Sandall) seemed to be very happy with this simple but sometimes powerful method for solving some of the NLP problems. The rationale is that because many NLP problems are more difficult to solve using the calculus-based methods, however, if we know the solution *domain*, we can divide this domain into many small parts and search every one of the parts to see which would give an optimized solution to the objective function, which is a function of the variables defining the domain. Hanna and Sandall(1995) provided a computer program (OPTSEARCH) to do this.

14 Calculus of variations and dynamic control theory

If the production process can be described in some continuous functions, the optimization problem is to find time path of a function, $y(t)$, where t stands for time, so that to optimize (max or min) another function. In Figure 10, the blue curve may represent some optimal time path (in contrast to any other possible paths which do not lead to optimized solution of the objective function).

This problem can be formulated using method of [Calculus of Variations](#), which was first developed in the Euler-Newton time. After a major publication by Russian mathematician

Figure 10: An illustration of dynamic programming in continuous form. The optimal time path $y(x)$ is shown by the blue curve. Here x represents time.

L.S. Pontryagin⁵⁶ in 1962, the modern cousin of the variational calculus began to be known as **Dynamic Control Theory**, with applications to a wide range of situations. Calculus of variations studies the influence of the infinitesimal change of a function, for example, $y(t)$, to the value of another function that is a function of, say, $y(t)$. The mathematical model of calculus of variations is stated as,

$$\text{Optimize } V[y] = \int_0^T F[t, y(t), y'(t)] dt \quad (119)$$

Subject to (Constraint function)

and

$$y(0) = A \quad \text{Initial state}$$

$$y(T) = Z \quad \text{Terminal state}$$

Here $V[y]$ is called the objective functional (e.g., function of a function). But sometimes it is written as $V(y)$. The integrand is a function of time t , $y(t)$, and $y'(t)$, which is the derivative of $y(t)$. The aim of the solution is to find a time path $y(t)$ that optimize $V[y]$. Obtaining this solution usually involves solving a second-order differential equation. If there are more than one state variables, or if the integrand contains higher order derivatives, then the solution involves a system of differential equations.

In economics, $V[y]$ can be total profit during a planning period, and $y(t)$ can be the time path of price. So, the objective is to find an optimal time path of price, so as to maximize the total profit during a specified time period.

⁵⁶I learned from somewhere he was a totally blind person

There is a good paper on plant succession under grazing pressure⁵⁷, using similar methods.

⁵⁷R. Huffaker and K. Cooper, 1995. Plant succession as a natural range restoration factor in private livestock enterprises. *Amer. J. Agr. Econ.* 77: 901-913.

15 Appendix

15.1 An Example for simulating a normal distribution using MINITAB

```
gmacro
transform

# MINITAB macro to generate normal distributions
# using the transformation method
# Shown on page 115 of Evans and Rosenthal (2004)
# (also described in Giordano and Nakanishi (2006) p516.

erase k1-k6
erase c1-c4

let k1= 1000 # N of random number

Random k1 c1;
  Uniform 0.0 1.0.      # Generate a uniform distribution in c1
Random k1 c2;
  Uniform 0.0 1.0.      # Generate a another uniform distribution in c2

# This is to simulate norm(0,1) using the two uniform (0,1)
# already been generated in c1 & c2 (see p215 of ER, 2004)

let c3=sqrt(2*log(1/c1))*cos(2*3.14159*c2)

# if  $X \sim (0,1)$ , then let  $Z = \sigma * x + \mu$ , we will have  $Z \sim (\mu, \sigma)$ 
# where,  $\mu$  is the mean and  $\sigma$  is stdev of this norm distribution
# here we assume  $\mu = 1$  and  $\sigma = 1$ 

let c4=c3+1
endmacro
```

15.2 An Example of rejection sampling for simulating an arbitrary distribution

This MINITAB macro simulates a Gaussian distribution $N(1,1)$ using the rejection method as described in Giordano and Nakanishi (2006), pages 517-518.

```
gmacro
rejection

let k1=10000
```

```

Random k1 c1;
  Uniform -2.0 4.0.
let k2=1/sqrt(2*3.14159)
let c2=k2*exp(-(c1-1)**2/2)

```

```

set c3
100
end

```

```

let k4=count(c3)+1
do k3=1:k1
  call ptest
  if c2(k3)>=c10(1)
    let c3(k4)=c1(k3)
    let k4=k4+1
  else
    next
  endif
enddo
delete 1 c3
endmacro

```

```

gmacro
ptest

```

```

Random 1 c10;
  Uniform 0 k2.
endmacro

```

15.3 Evaluating a definite integral by sampling a uniform distribution

```

gmacro
uniform

```

```

# MINITAB macro to implement Monte Carlo approximate of
# integral  $I = \int_0^1 (\cos(x^2) \sin(x^4)) dx$ 
# Shown on page 214 of Evans and Rosenthal (2004)
# problem 4.5.3

```

```

let k1= 1000 # N of random number
call unif

```

```

let k1= 10000 # N of random number

```

```

call unif

let k1= 100000 # N of random number
call unif
endmacro

gmacro
unif

# to generate uniform distribution in order to simulate and integral
# as shown in the main.

Random k1 c1;
  Uniform 0.0 1.0.

let c2=cos(c1**2)*sin(c1**4)
let k2=mean(c2)
let k3=stdev(c2)
let k4=k2-3*k3/sqrt(k1)
let k5=k2+3*k3/sqrt(k1)
name k1 'N' k2 'M_n' k3 'S' k4 'lowerB' k5 'higherB'
name c1 'u' c2 'T_i'
print k1-k5
endmacro

```

15.4 Evaluating a definite integral by sampling an exponential distribution

```

gmacro
exponent

# MINITAB macro to implement Monte Carlo approximation of
# integral  $I = \int_0^{\infty} (25 x^2 \cos(x^2) e^{-25x}) dx$ 
# Shown on page 214 of Evans and Rosenthal (2004)
# problem 4.5.4

erase k1-k5
erase c1-c3

let k1= 1000 # N of random number
call ex

let k1= 10000 # N of random number
call ex

```

```

let k1= 100000 # N of random number
call ex

erase k1-k5
erase c1-c3
endmacro

gmacro
ex

# to generate exponential distribution in order to simulate the integral
# as shown in the main

Random k1 c1;
  Uniform 0.0 1.0.

let c2=-loge(c1)/25
let c3=c2**2*cos(c2**2)
let k2=mean(c3)
let k3=stdev(c3)
let k4=k2-3*k3/sqrt(k1)
let k5=k2+3*k3/sqrt(k1)
name k1 'N' k2 'M_n' k3 'S' k4 'lowerB' k5 'higherB'
name c1 'u_i' c2 'x_i' c3 'T_i'
print k1-k5
endmacro

```

15.5 Evaluating a definite integral by sampling a normal distribution

```

gmacro
normal

# MINITAB macro to implement Monte Carlo approximation of
# integral  $I = \int_0^{\infty} \sin(x) e^{-x^2/2} dx$ 
# Shown on page 216 of Evans and Rosenthal (2004)
# problem 4.5.6

erase k1-k6
erase c1-c4

let k1= 1000 # N of random number
call no

```

```

let k1= 10000 # N of random number
call no

# N of random number!!!! this part is very slow (need 15 minutes!)
let k1= 100000
call no

erase k1-k6
erase c1-c4
endmacro

gmacro
no

# to generate normal(0,1) distribution in order to simulate the integral
# as shown in the main

Random k1 c1;
  Uniform 0.0 1.0.      # Generate a uniform distribution in c1

Random k1 c2;
  Uniform 0.0 1.0.      # Generate a another uniform distribution in c2

# This is to simulate norm(0,1) using the two distributions of uniform (0,1)
# already been generated in c1 & c2 (see p215 of ER, 2004)

let c3=sqrt(2*log(1/c1))*cos(2*3.14159*c2)
do k6 = 1:k1
  if c3(k6) > 0
    let c4(k6) = sin(c3(k6))
  else
    let c4(k6) = 0
  endif
enddo

let k2=mean(c4)*sqrt(2*3.14159)
let k3=3*sqrt(k2*(1-k2)/k1)
let k4=k2-k3
let k5=k2+k3
name k1 'N' k2 'M_n' k3 'S' k4 'lowerB' k5 'higherB'
# same code as in page 216 of ER 2004
name c1 'u_i' c2 'v_i' c3 'X_i' c4 'T_i'
print k1-k5
endmacro

```

15.6 Evaluating a definite integral using the transformation method and the trapezoidal rule

```
gmacro
compare

# To compare Monte Carlo method and the trapezoidal
# rule in estimating definite integral
#  $I = \int_0^1 \sin(x) e^{-x^2/2} dx$ .

# First use monte carlo approximation.
let k1=10000

random k1 c1;
  uniform 0.0 1.0.

random k1 c2;
  uniform 0.0 1.0.

let c3=sqrt(2*log(1/c1))*cos(2*3.14159*c2)

do k6=1:k1
  if c3(k6)>0 and c3(k6)<1
    let c4(k6)=sin(c3(k6))
  else
    let c4(k6)=0
  endif
enddo

let k2=mean(c4)*sqrt(2*3.14159)
let k3=3*sqrt(k2*(1-k2)/k1)

let k4=k2-k3
let k5=k2+k3
name k1 'n' k2'M_n' k3 'S' k4 'lowerb' k5 'lighb'

note Result from Monte Carlo Approximation
print k1-k5

# Next we estimate the integral with the trapezoidal rule
# using formula:  $I = (b-a)/(2n)*[f(x_0)+2f(x_1)+\dots+2f(x_{n-1})+ f(x_n)]$ ,
# where  $a=0$ ,  $b=1$ ,  $n=10000$ ,  $f(x_0)$  is the function a value
# at  $x=a=0$ ;  $f(x_n)$  is the function value at  $x=n$ ;
#  $f(x_1), \dots, f(x_{n-1})$ , are function values at the internal nodes.
```

```

# Remember k1= n is used here also
let k8=0 # =a
let k9=1 # =b
let k12=(k9-k8)/k1 # =delta x

do k10=0:k1 # do loop to generate x value for each of the n+1 nodes
  let k13=k10+1
  let c10(k13)=k8+k10*(k9-k8)/k1
enddo

let c11=sin(c10)*exp(-1*c10**2/2)
let k14=count(c11)
let k15=sum(c11)
let k15=2*k15-c11(1)-c11(k14)
let k15=k15*(k9-k8)/(2*k1)
name k15 'I_traped'

note
note Result from using the trapedoizal rule
print k15

endmacro

```

15.7 A True Basic program for approximating the value of pi

```

! pai
! This program is to approximate the value of pi
! using the Monte Carlo method
! Assume the radius of a circle is 1 and the origin is set to the center
! of the circle.

randomize

OPEN #1: NAME "DATA", ORG TEXT, CREATE NEWOLD, ACCESS OUTPUT
print #1: "N", "estimated PAI"
print
dim x(1),y(1),samples(15),z(15)

mat read samples
data 100,500,1000,1500,3000,5000,7500,10000,10500,12000,15000,20000,50000,100000,150000

FOR j = 1 to 15
  let n = samples(j)
  mat redim x(n),y(n)

  FOR i = 1 to n

```

```

    let x(i) = RND
    let y(i) = RND
NEXT i

let C = 0

FOR i = 1 to n
  let a = (x(i)^2 + y(i)^2)^0.5
  if a < 1 THEN
    let C = C + 1
  end if
NEXT i

let z(j) = 4*C/n
print #1: n,z(j)
NEXT j
end

```

15.8 A MINITAB macro for approximating the volume of a ball with radius 1

```

gmacro
ball

# This MINITAB macro is to approximate the volume of a ball
# using the Monte Carlo method
# Assume radius is 1 and the origin of the 3-d coordinates is set to the center
# of the ball
#let k2 = 1000
#call b

let k2=20000
call b
#erase k1-k6
#erase c1-c3
endmacro

gmacro
b

let k1 = 0

Random k2 c1;
  Uniform 0.0 1.0.
Random k2 c2;

```

```

Uniform 0.0 1.0.
Random k2 c3;
Uniform 0.0 1.0.

do k3 = 1:k2
  let k5=c1(k3)**2 + c2(k3)**2 + c3(k3)**2
  if sqrt(k5) < 1
    let k1 = k1 + 1
  else
    next
  endif
enddo

let k4=8*k1/k2
let k6=4/3*3.14159
name k2 'N' k4 'estimate' k6 'true'
print k2 k4 k6
endmacro

```

15.9 A MINITAB macro for approximating the value of e using the Monte Carlo method

```

gmacro
euler

# This MINITAB macro is to approximate the universal number e
# using the Monte Carlo method
# As suggested by GN (2006), we start with evaluating the definite integral
#  $\int_1^{10} (1/x) dx$ , which equals  $\log_e(10)$ 
#let k2 = 1000
#call eu

let k2=20000
call eu
erase k1-k5
erase c1-c2
endmacro

gmacro
eu

let k1 = 0
Random k2 c1;          # generate values for x
Uniform 1.0 10.0.

```

```

Random k2 c2;
  Uniform 0.1 1.0.      # generate values for y=1/x

do k3 = 1:k2
  if c2(k3) <= 1/c1(k3)
    let k1 = k1 + 1
  else
    next
  endif
enddo

let k4 = k2 / (k2 + 8.1 * k1)  # rectangle area is 9*0.9 = 8.1
let k5 = 10**(k4)
name k2 'N' k5 'e-est'
print k2 k5
endmacro

```

15.10 A MINITAB macro for recursively simulating a posterior probability

```

gmacro
bayes1

# For example on page 39 of Chorin and hald (2006)
# A: event that eta1 + eta2 = 1
# Our prior distribution is:
# p = 1/4 with probability of 1/4; p = 1/2 with probability 3/4.
# To do this problem using the second form of the Bayes' theorem,
# we consider the sampling space OMEGA as partitioned into Z1 and Z2
# with Z1 be the event that p = 1/4, and Z2 be the event that p = 1/2.
# We consider the probability of Z1 (that is p = 1/4) given A (that is
# eta1 + eta2 = 1).

let k1=2*(1/4)*(3/4) # P(A|Z1)
let k2=2*(1/2)*(1/2) # P(A|Z2)
let k3=1/4 # Prior probability for Z1 (prob that p=0.25 is 1/4)

set c1
  100
end

let k11=count(c1)+1
let k10=0

```

```

while k10=0
  let k4=k1*k3/(k1*k3+k2*(1-k3))
  let c1(k11)=k3
  let c2(k11)=k4
  let k11=k11+1
  let k3=k4

  if k4<0.01 or k4>0.99
    let k10=1
  endif
endwhile

delete 1 c1-c2
name c1 'Prior_Z1' c2 'posterior_Z1'
erase k1-k11
endmacro

```

15.11 A MINITAB macro for simulating transpiration ratio of plant leaves

```

macro
CT_1971 aoh warm cool wide narrow ri4 ri3 windy calm

# Author: Xuejun Dong
# Texas A&M AgriLife Research at Uvalde, TX USA
# email: xuejun.dong@ag.tamu.edu
# First created: 15 November 2020
# Last updated: 17 November 2020

# This MINITAB macro, tested on MINITAB Version 17,
# demonstrates Cowan and Troughton's model describing
# the relative influences of stomata on transpiration and
# photosynthesis.
# Reference: I. R. Cowan and J. H. Troughton 1971. The relative role of
# stomata in transpiration and photosynthesis. Planta, 97, 325-336.

# The usefulness of this macro is that it allows the user to visualize the
# outcome of realized transpiration ratio as a function of different
# combinations of the nine influencing parameters (described below),
# when the relative magnitudes of leaf internal resistance and leaf
# boundary layer resistance change, considering the coupled fluxes of
# heat and water vapor in plant leaves during photosynthesis under
# field conditions.

```

```

# Once required data are provided by the user, the macro will generate
# four sub-figures describing the relationship between transpiration ratio
# (i.e., ratio of relative transpiration rate and relative
# photosynthetic rate) and relative photosynthetic rate for a relatively
# large, vs. small leaf of a hypothetical C4 and C3 plant under following
# conditions:
#
# sub-figure (a) - warm and windy (ww),
# sub-figure (b) - warm and calm (wc),
# sub-figure (c) - cool and windy (cw),
# sub-figure (d) - cool and calm (cc).

# How to use it?
# The user need to provide specific values for the nine plant and
# environmental variables influencing parameter alpha, which is defined
# in Eq. (9) of Cowan and Troughton (1971). These nine numerical values
# must be provided in the exact order as specified below (either integer
# or decimal numbers are fine):

# aoh - "0" for amphistomatous leaves and "1" for hypostomatous leaves
# warm - a warm temperature (in degrees C)
# cool - a cool temperature (in degrees C)
# wide - a large leaf width in centimeters (cm)
# narrow - a small leaf width in centimeters (cm)
# ri4 - internal resistance to photosynthesis for a C4 plant (<= 1 s/cm)
# ri3 - internal resistance to photosynthesis for a C3 plant (2-10 s/cm)
# windy - a moderately high wind speed (unit in m/s)
# calm - a moderately low wind speed (unit in m/s)
#
# Assume this macro is saved as a text file "CT_1971.mac" under C:\ Drive
# of personel computer with Windows, it can be invoked by:
# '%C:\CT_1971' 0 30 20 10 1 0.8 5.5 4 0.5 followed by ENTER.

# The above command will assign the following values to the nine variables
# aoh = 0 (an amphistomatous leaf); warm = 30 degrees C; cool = 20 degr C;
# wide = 10 cm leaf; narrow = 1 cm leaf; ri4 = 0.8 s/cm; ri3 = 5.5 s/cm;
# windy = 4 m/s; calm = 0.5 m/s.

mconstant aoh warm cool wide narrow ri4 ri3 windy calm
mconstant ri size rc u eps T alpha i fnum weath
mcolumn x y.1-y.16 z.1-z.16

set x
  0:1/0.02
end

```

```

let x(1) = 0.00001

do i = 1:16
  if i = 1 or i = 2 or i = 3 or i = 4
    let T = warm
    let u = windy
  elseif i = 5 or i = 6 or i = 7 or i = 8
    let T = warm
    let u = calm
  elseif i = 9 or i = 10 or i = 11 or i = 12
    let T = cool
    let u = windy
  else
    let T = cool
    let u = calm
  endif

  if i = 1 or i = 5 or i = 9 or i = 13
    let size = wide
    let ri = ri4
  elseif i = 2 or i = 6 or i = 10 or i = 14
    let size = wide
    let ri = ri3
  elseif i = 3 or i = 7 or i = 11 or i = 15
    let size = narrow
    let ri = ri4
  else
    let size = narrow
    let ri = ri3
  endif

  let rc = 3.4 * sqrt(size/(100*u))
  let eps = 0.6649 + 0.0226*T + 0.00258*T**2

  if aoh = 0
    let alpha = (ri/rc + 0.5)/(0.66*eps + 0.58) # Amphistomatous
  elseif aoh = 1
    let alpha = (ri/rc + 1)/(0.66*eps + 1.17) # Hypostomatous
  else
    let alpha = (ri/rc + 0.5)/(0.66*eps + 0.58)
  endif

  let y.i = x/(alpha + (1-alpha) * x)
  let z.i = y.i/x
enddo

```

```

name z.1 'Wide.C4.ww' z.2 'Wide.C3.ww' z.3 'Narrow.C4.ww' z.4 'Narrow.C3.ww'
name z.5 'Wide.C4.wc' z.6 'Wide.C3.wc' z.7 'Narrow.C4.wc' z.8 'Narrow.C3.wc'
name z.9 'Wide.C4.cw' z.10 'Wide.C3.cw' z.11 'Narrow.C4.cw' z.12 'Narrow.C3.cw'
name z.13 'Wide.C4.cc' z.14 'Wide.C3.cc' z.15 'Narrow.C4.cc' z.16 'Narrow.C3.cc'
# These 16 constants do not need to be declared!

```

Layout.

```

kkset fnum "(a)", weath "warm-windy (ww)" # kkset can set multiple text constants!
call graf x z.1-z.4 0 0.5 0.5 1 fnum weath

```

```

kkset fnum "(b)", weath "warm-calm (wc)"
call graf x z.5-z.8 0.5 1 0.5 1 fnum weath

```

```

kkset fnum "(c)", weath "cool-windy (cw)"
call graf x z.9-z.12 0 0.5 0 0.5 fnum weath

```

```

kkset fnum "(d)", weath "cool-calm (cc)"
call graf x z.13-z.16 0.5 1 0 0.5 fnum weath

```

EndLayout.

endmacro

macro

```

graf xx z1 z2 z3 z4 xs xe ys ye fnum weath

```

Subroutine to specify common features of the sub-figures

```

mconstant xs xe ys ye fnum weath

```

```

mcolumn xx z1 z2 z3 z4

```

```

plot z1*xx z2*xx z3*xx z4*xx;

```

```

Title weath;

```

```

Footnote fnum;

```

```

  tsize 1.5;

```

```

  noitalic;

```

```

Figure xs xe ys ye;

```

```

axlabel 1 "Relative assimilation (a)";

```

```

  tsize 1.2;

```

```

axlabel 2 "Transpiration ratio (e/a)";

```

```

  tsize 1.2;

```

```

tick 1;

```

```

  tsize 1.1;

```

```

tick 2;

```

```

  tsize 1.1;

```

```

  nmajor 7;

```

```

scale 2;

```

```

    max 3.08;
    min -0.05;
Connect;
Overlay.
endmacro

```

15.12 A MINITAB macro for carrying out pivoting in solving a system of linear equations

```

macro
pvt i j x.1-x.n

# Author X. Dong
# November 23, 2020

# This macro completes the solving-substitution process
# for the solution of a LP problem by
# exchanging one of the current non-basic variables with a basic
# variable and updating the coefficient matrix.
# The macro is adapted from the global macro PIVOT by
# W. Fox, F. R. Giordano, S. L. Madox and M. D. Weir. (1987).
# Mathematical Modeling with MINITAB. Brooks/Cole Publishing Company.
# Monterey, CA. USA.

# Assume the current coefficient matrix has n-1 variables, x_1, x_2,
# ..., x_(n-1), and x_i and x_j are the new basic variables to
# solve for. Out of these n-1 variables, x_(n-1) actually is a dummy
# variable, which is considered as a basic variable and never
# exchanged with any of the non-basic variables.

# The user is expected to manually enter the current
# coefficient matrix in c1-cn, with the last column being RHS,
# and last row the objective function with the negative of its current
# value placed at last column position, i.e., in cn.
# For example, if the new basic variables are going to be x_2 and x_3,
# and we have 6 variables (n=7), the following command can be used to
# to invoke the macro (assuming it is saved as "pvt.mac" under c:\).
# %'C:\pvt' 2 3 c1-c7      followed by ENTER
mconstant i j n nm
mcolumn x.1-x.n
mmatrix m1 m2

let nm=n-1

```

```
copy x.i x.j x.nm m1
copy x.1-x.n m2
inve m1 m1
mult m1 m2 m2
copy m2 x.1-x.n
print x.1-x.n

endmacro
```